

METEOR-Berichte

Azores Plateau

Cruise No. M128

02.07.2016 – 27.07.2016,
Ponta Delgada (Azores, Portugal) – Ponta Delgada (Azores, Portugal)

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Editorial Assistance:

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1 Summary

The research program of cruise M128 Azores Plateau mainly aimed at improving our understanding of the igneous and tectonic processes that occur during the initial emplacement of large igneous plateaus and the subsequent interaction between intraplate volcanism and ultraslow rifting. The sampling program targeted the oldest and youngest igneous volcanic edifices in the Azores to better constrain the age of the submarine Plateau and the processes that led to changes in the magmatic activity. We obtained a total of more than 330 rock samples and more than 435 biological specimens during 70 TV grab stations (63 containing samples) and 19 successful ROV dives. The combination of bathymetric maps (1980 km hydroacoustic profile length) and petrological samples allows us to better constrain the evolution of rift systems in this tectonically and magmatically active region. A major sampling focus were the volcanic rift systems west of the islands along the Terceira Rift axis and west of São Jorge and Faial. In addition, six stratigraphic dive profiles will yield important constraints on the early magmatic evolution of the Azores Plateau. The samples and geochemical, petrological, volcanological and biological data will provide a unique and detailed picture of how and when the Azores submarine Plateau formed and the extent to which the local tectonic processes influenced the formation and ascent of melts. The macrofauna samples will yield detailed information on the function of the Azores Plateau as a bathymetric swell in the Central Atlantic Ocean.

Zusammenfassung

Das Arbeitsprogramm der Ausfahrt M128 Azores Plateau war im Wesentlichen auf das Verständnis der magmatischen und tektonischen Prozesse ausgerichtet, die bei der initialen Bildung großer magmatischer Provinzen eine Rolle spielen. Zusätzlich sollen die Prozesse untersucht werden, die bei der Interaktion zwischen Intraplattenvulkanismus und langsamen Spreizungsbewegungen bedeutsam sind. Die Beprobung zielte auf die ältesten und jüngsten magmatischen Strukturen in den Azoren, um das Alter des submarinen Plateaus besser zu bestimmen, sowie die Prozesse zu untersuchen, die zu einer Veränderung der magmatischen Aktivität führen. Im Rahmen der Fahrt wurden 70 Stationen mit dem videogeführten Greifer (63 mit Gesteinsproben) und 19 erfolgreiche ROV-Tauchgänge durchgeführt, die mehr als 330 Gesteins- und mehr als 435 biologische Proben mit an Bord brachten. Die Kombination der bathymetrischen Karten (1980 km Profillänge) und der Gesteinsproben wird es uns erlauben, zum Verständnis der Entwicklung von Riftsystemen in dieser tektonisch und magmatisch aktiven Region beizutragen. Ein wesentlicher Fokus der Arbeiten während der Fahrt M128 lag deshalb im langsam-spreizenden Terceira Rift und dort im Wesentlichen westlich der Inseln. Zusätzlich wurden die westlichen vulkanischen Riftzonen von São Jorge und Faial untersucht. Sechs stratigraphische Profile erlauben erstmals Einblicke in die älteren Bereiche des Azorenplateaus. Insgesamt wird die Kombination aus petrologischen, vulkanologischen und biologischen Daten ein einmaliges und detailliertes Bild über die zeitliche Abfolge, die Ursache und die Entwicklung des Magmatismus ergeben. Insbesondere die detaillierten Karten und die enge Beprobung werden wichtige Erkenntnisse über die Beziehung zwischen den tektonischen Strukturen und der Bildung und dem Aufstieg von Schmelzen des submarinen Azorenplateaus liefern. Die beprobten Makrofaunen werden zudem Informationen darüber geben, wie wichtig die Rolle des Azoren Plateaus als bathymetrische Anomalie für die Ökologie im Zentralatlantik ist.

2 Participants

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3 Research Program

The research program of M128 had the main objective of sampling and mapping both, the oldest and youngest volcanic edifices of the Azores identified during previous cruises (Pos232, Pos286, M79/2, M113) but not sampled to date. The rock sampling targeted numerous young, historically to recently volcanically active structures (João de Castro seamount, Serreta, Capelinhos, W of Graciosa) but also aimed at the older volcanic sequences that were sampled in the basins north of João de Castro, between Terceira and Graciosa, west of São Miguel, along the East Azores Fracture Zone and at Princesa Alice bank to better constrain the initial formation, timing and evolution of the Azores Plateau. The combination of hydroacoustic data and petrological samples allows us for the first time to better constrain the evolution of rift systems in this tectonically and magmatically active region. During and after the cruise we aim to test the following hypotheses with our working program:

- Relatively incompatible element depleted tholeiitic lavas form the lower part of the Azores Plateau and reflect enhanced melting either in a plume head or when the Azores plume appeared beneath the MAR. The deeper portions of the plateau were sampled by ROV at steep slopes along the seismically inactive East Azores Fracture Zone, Princesa Alice bank and on the flanks of the deeps of the Terceira Rift.
- The lavas from the deep part of the entire Azores Plateau have about similar ages (~10 Ma?) reflecting one event of voluminous flood basalt volcanism. Age dating of the samples taken in the deepest stratigraphic levels of the Azores Plateau yield important insights into the formation of this plateau and oceanic plateaus in general. Since the Azores Plateau is an important ecological habitat in the Central Northern Atlantic, and is situated in the major Atlantic currents the emplacement age has implications for changes of the ocean currents and potentially also climatic changes.
- Compositional changes occur within the flood basalts reflecting variations in melting and fractional crystallization processes. The stratigraphic sampling of the uppermost kilometre of the Azores Plateau by ROV and TV grab and the data obtained on these samples allows us to constrain these variations.

- The younger and older rift zones display different orientations on the Azores Plateau. We have sampled these edifices by ROV and TV grab at João de Castro, Capelinhos and Pico Ridge. Dating will later reveal when these changes occurred and whether this may be related to large scale structural changes in the Azores.
- The young eruption events occurred along dikes connected to larger volcanic structures and produced pillow lavas reflecting relatively low lava eruption rates. We have performed detailed hydroacoustic and geological surveys of the youngest volcanic edifices (Serreta, João de Castro, Capelinhos).
- We aimed to test whether the high volatile content of the Azorean magmas affects the hydrothermal venting and possibly leads to very high CO₂ contents in the fluids. Unfortunately, we did not find any evidence for the occurrence of recent hydrothermal activity and previous interpretations of active degassing on the flanks of João de Castro seamount may have to be considered with caution.
- A description of deep-sea biological assemblages required further voucher specimens to be collected for taxonomy as many dominant species remain beyond simple visual recognition. Biological collections have been made of voucher biological specimens sampled by ROV and TV grab. Particular attention was given to dominant organisms that are known only from imagery and require taxonomic validation in the lab.
- High-resolution surveys conducted on the selected bathyal areas suggest that the occurrence of assemblages dominated by habitat-building species may be patchier than broad-scale models forecast. The enhanced knowledge of the topography derived from the hydroacoustic surveys combined with the in situ imagery and samples collected during the ROV dives in previously unexplored geomorphological contexts will be a significant contribution towards the statistical modelling of species and habitats local and regional distribution. Such detailed information is currently in high demand for (i) marine spatial planning at regional scales as well as for (ii) the design of zonation schemes at marine protected area scales.
- Another aim of the cruise was to combine volcanological, geophysical, petrological, hydrothermal, and biodiversity studies on the young submarine rift zones of the Azores volcanoes along the Terceira Rift west of São Miguel, at João de Castro, and to the west of Terceira, Graciosa and Faial. These samples will provide the basis for increasing our understanding of the transport of melts from the mantle to the crust and potentially into hydrothermal systems and to the biosphere.
- The submarine rift zones along the Terceira Rift are probably connected by dikes to the magma systems of the subaerial volcanoes and this connection can be tested using geochemistry and petrology. Using ROV, wax corer, TV-grab, and hydroacoustic surveys to map and study these sites in detail offers the possibility to determine the composition of lavas, their volume and the volcanic processes of their formation.
- It has been suggested that the Azores volcanism is caused by anomalously high volatile contents in the mantle as have been found in basalts on the neighbouring Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Explosive eruptions are known from volatile-rich magmas even at great water depths and it was speculated that the 1998-2001 Serreta eruption (west of Terceira) formed submarine lava fountains and lava lakes (Gaspar et al., 2003). During our ROV

dives we did find evidence for explosive eruptions along a fissure at the submarine Serreta volcano.

- If the Azores volcanism formed due to a mantle “wetspot” then the H₂O and CO₂ contents in the magmas should be high and we need to study melt inclusions in minerals and possibly glassy submarine lavas in fresh samples from Serreta, João de Castro and Capelinhos. We intend to study the volatile content in young submarine lavas in order to test the hypothesis of an Azores “wetspot”. So far, sampling of glassy lavas by dredging has been difficult and fortuitous and only few samples suitable for determination of H₂O and CO₂ have been recovered. The sampling by ROV and TV-grab yields better results and numerous fresh glassy samples were recovered during M128.

An additional hydroacoustic survey and sampling profile targeted the area W of Graciosa aiming at the triple junction of the Eurasian, African and American Plates and the structural and geological evolution of the ultraslow spreading Terceira rift axis.

In general, the sampling strategy was based on the multibeam surveys of M79/2, M113 and M128 on a daily basis. The sampling was preferentially done by Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV QUEST 4000) and TV grab to ensure consistent and accurate sampling as well as structural and geological control of the sampling. During the TV grab sampling we used Miniature Autonomous Plume Recorders (MAPR) devices provided by the Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory of NOAA. These recorders of turbidity, E_H and temperature were aimed at detecting potential hydrothermally sources turbidity and Eh-anomalies in the water column in the vicinity of the Azores.

4 Narrative of the Cruise

(Beier, C.)

A delegation of scientists from the GeoZentrum Nordbayern of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg and the entire ROV MARUM QUEST team arrived on the 28th of June and started installing the ROV and the TV grab onboard RV METEOR on the 29th of June. The majority of the scientific party joined on the 30.06.2016 and the entire scientific party boarded the ship on Friday, the 1st of July 2016. During port stay the installations for the Remotely Operated Vehicle QUEST (ROV QUEST), the TV grab (TVG) and the volcanic wax corer (VSR) were done and the labs were prepared for operations at sea.

On Saturday the 2nd of July, RV METEOR left Ponta Delgada harbour at 9 am and reached the open sea only a few minutes later with calm seas and little wind (Fig. 4.1). The scientific program started at 9:25 am with hydroacoustic surveys along the southern coast and west of São Miguel. A hydroacoustic profile along the western volcano of Sete Cidades was carried out in an attempt to determine if any hydrothermal gas flares were evident in the EM 710 hydroacoustic data followed by two successful TV grabs on the northern and southern volcanic rift zones west of São Miguel. These TV grabs sampled the youngest submarine rift structures of São Miguel island, a potential ROV target for the dives on the 17 and 18th of July. Both TV grabs contained

relatively fresh volcanic rock samples along with glassy pillow rim fragments. During the night of the 2nd to the 3rd of July the scientific program continued with a multibeam survey along the northern rift shoulder of the Hirondele Basin between São Miguel and Terceira in order to complete the detailed bathymetric map until the end of the cruise. During the morning, RV METEOR headed south towards João de Castro seamount, a major scientific target that was sampled until the night of the 6th to 7th July. Historic eruptions and numerous seismic events were described from João de Castro seamount, which made it a suitable target for investigating one of the youngest magmatic edifices in the Azores.

During the 3rd of July, we performed five successful TV grabs recovering a large variety of both magmatic and sedimentary rocks from the northern, western and eastern part of João de Castro. In the night of the 3rd and early morning of the 4th of July, a hydroacoustic profile was mapped SE of Terceira covering a major part of the Terceira Rift axis, which revealed the horst and graben structures across the rift. Most of these structures may solely be of tectonic origin and did not show any evidence in the multibeam data for recent magmatic activity.

The first ROV dive started in the morning of the 4th of July along the eastern edge of João de Castro seamount in a water depth of 400 m close to the site from where Cardigos et al. (2005) had previously reported flares of gas bubbles in the water column. The dive resulted in 12 hard rock and lapilli samples but revealed no active hydrothermal activity. The abundant macrofauna cover on the lavas implies the absence of recent volcanic activity in this area. During the night of the 4th of July and in the morning of the 5th of July the TV grab was used to sample the smaller volcanic cones south of the seamount and its north-western rift zone. The samples taken show that the southern and north-western edifices have not been volcanically active recently.

Fig. 4.1: Overview map of ship track of cruise M128 Azores Plateau.

During the morning of the 5th of July, ROV sampling of the graben shoulder of the rift system 18 km north of João de Castro aimed at stratigraphic sampling of the older lavas of the Azores Plateau. The ROV imaging and the sampling revealed numerous blocky outcrops of volcanic rock samples intercalated with shallower sandy sections. The dive finished in the evening hours after 13 rock samples were recovered along with biological samples that could potentially contain new species. This stratigraphic profile was then continued on the 15th of July.

During the night of the 5th of July until the morning of the 6th of July, we successfully carried out five TV grabs along the central, eastern and north-eastern part of João de Castro, which resulted in numerous pillow lavas, scoriaceous blocks and consolidated ash layers, indicating that the rift system cutting João de Castro in the east is part of the active rift, whereas the western and north-western rift systems are seemingly extinct.

The morning of Wednesday the 6th of July was used to perform an ROV dive in the north of João de Castro, about 2.2 miles north of the summit in a water depth of 850 m. This dive revealed young volcanic features with pillow lavas, sheet flows, lapilli, consolidated ash and little macrofauna. We interpret this to be the result of young volcanic activity at João de Castro and an area that may also be the source of recent seismic activity observed. During the night to Thursday the 7th of July, RV METEOR carried out a multibeam survey west of the island of Terceira in the Serreta area, one of the youngest submarine eruption sites in the Azores (1998-2001). A morning ROV dive was delayed by the fact that we found numerous fishing lines, fishing boats and buoys in the immediate vicinity of the diving area. After a successful TV grab NW of Serreta we managed to have the ROV on the ocean floor at 600 m water depth NW of Serreta. After a successful dive with numerous samples consisting of fresh glassy lavas and lapilli, we lowered two TV grabs northwest of Serreta. One grab 6 miles NW of Serreta revealed sediments covering the younger rift system, while a successful grab closer to the young volcanic ridge contained several fresh and glassy pillow lava fragments. This led us to conclude that the magmatic activity is indeed focussed along narrow rift zones similar to João de Castro. We then headed south overnight to seek shelter from increasing swell and winds.

The next ROV dive started in the morning of the 8th of July at the submarine Pico Ridge off the island of Pico, which was extensively sampled. However, due to increasing winds and waves the ROV dive was finished at midday and we continued sampling Pico Ridge by TV grab. During the night from the 8th to the 9th of July, we continued a multibeam profile towards Terceira and then did an ROV profile at the northern Terceira basin in the morning of the 9th of July. This profile targeted the older Azores Plateau lavas to determine the exact timing of the initial formation of the first alkaline lavas in the Azores in order to constrain when and how the Azores Plateau formed. The profile covered some 800 m elevation change, and 12 samples were taken during the dive, comprising pillow lavas, sheet flows, and lava tubes. This profile will be used to increase our understanding of the initial formation of the Azores Plateau along with the samples along the East Azores Fracture Zone. The following night we conducted a hydroacoustic survey of the basin west of the island of Terceira aiming at the structures of the rifting processes.

The morning of Sunday the 10th of July started with a slow hydroacoustic survey across the submarine Serreta volcano before we started diving in one of the bathymetric deeps of this young

submarine volcano. The dive revealed abundant fresh lava fragments with little to no fauna. Numerous fish swarms were observed surrounding the ROV. The dive targeted the crater walls in the south, a small wall in the west and to small cones along the northern part of the fissure. The ROV finally arrived at the surface with some 15 rock samples and two biological specimen on-board.

We continued with a short hydroacoustic survey north and south of Serreta. During the night we conducted three successful TV grabs crossing the entity of the Serreta volcanic ridge. The samples included fresh, glassy pillow lavas, massive aphyric lavas and scoriaceous lavas. The sampling along Serreta revealed that the volcano does not consist of a crater row as previously suggested but instead is a volcanic ridge where older eruptions took place in the northern part, while the most recent eruptions occurred in the south. After an additional small bathymetric survey across Serreta, we decided to improve our understanding of Serreta with an additional dive along the southern flank. Unfortunately, the dive was delayed by the presence of fishermen. The ROV was lowered into the water at lunchtime after maritime police had finally cleared the area. This dive on the 11th of July crossed the southern fissure revealing sites of previous low-temperature hydrothermal activity and numerous fresh rock samples. Indications of former hydrothermal activity were presumed bacterial mats and sulphur precipitates; no temperature anomalies were detected, nor was there any sign of shimmering water. The TV grab was used to extensively sample the volcanic system of Serreta overnight. This sampling revealed that, from its western edifice to the youngest samples in the east, the Serreta volcanic system extends for 4.2 km from east to west, but is only some 1.2 km wide. In the morning of the 12th of July, we aimed to conduct another dive at the eastern part of the Serreta volcanic ridge. However, due to technical problems the dive was delayed and commenced at lunchtime. This dive covered the south-eastern end of the Serreta fissure and revealed that the eruption in 1998-2001 covered a length of up to 2.78 km. Two TV grabs 7 to 13 km north of Serreta recovered sandy sediments and carbonates, indicating that much of the rifting west of Terceira is solely tectonic in nature and that the magmatic activity may be focussed towards narrow rift zones.

The night from Tuesday (12th) to Wednesday (13th) and the entire Wednesday were used to perform a hydroacoustic survey along the northern coastline of Graciosa heading west towards the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. This survey was aimed at mapping the current plate triple junction between the Eurasian, African and American Plates. We will use the bathymetric maps to better constrain the structural nature of the volcanoes and crust east of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Our findings indicate that the first N-S striking structures that may be related to the Mid-Atlantic Ridge occur some 50 km west of Graciosa, however, are being interrupted by NW-SE trending rift basins that may best be explained by shearing and extension of the ultraslow spreading Terceira Rift axis. Unfortunately, sampling the seamounts some 40 km east of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge was unsuccessful as a result of technical problems with the TV grab and the hard surfaces impeding any sampling.

The multibeam survey continued until the 14th of July in the morning, when we started an ROV dive west of Graciosa. This dive aimed at the westernmost extension of the rift system, where we had suspected young volcanic activity, but the sedimentation and the lithologies discovered imply that this rift system was not site of any young volcanic or tectonic activity. The presence

of an inactive rift system is difficult to reconcile with the occurrence of an island that experienced volcanic activity between 0.7 and 0.06 Ma and is also known for its fumaroles.

During the night from the 14th to the 15th we continued with a multibeam survey south of Graciosa and Terceira towards north of João de Castro seamount. We continued a stratigraphic profile started on the 5th of July now from 1960 m water depth to 1200 m. The ROV images revealed that the upper part of this graben shoulder consisted of extremely steep and large outcrops of pillow lavas, intercalated with sediments and lava flows. The ROV dive was successful with 22 samples and the entire profile consists now of 35 samples over 1250 m elevation allowing unique constraints on the evolution of the Azores Plateau.

The night of the 15th and morning of the 16th a hydroacoustic survey along the northern Hirondele Basin targeted the site of a historic eruption (1882) described in this vicinity before heading towards the western coastline of Sete Cidades volcano at São Miguel. The hydroacoustic survey here targeted potential dive areas for the next days. We arrived in the harbour of Ponta Delgada the evening of the 16th of July and stayed the night in port before heading out for the 30-year RV METEOR anniversary cruise with members of the German Research Foundation, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, the Leitstelle Deutsche Forschungsschiffe in Hamburg and the German Parliament. The dive on the 17th of July was performed west of the island of São Miguel and targeted a potentially young rift zone volcano. The dive (dive #400 of MARUM QUEST 4000) revealed numerous lava flows and pillow lavas with a high density of fauna on top of the lava flows. The dive was interrupted by a fishing line caught in the ROV's cable. The line was cut to continue the dive.

During the afternoon hours of the 17th of July we drove back to Ponta Delgada to allow the guests to disembark before heading back to the rift zones west of São Miguel. During the night and in the early mornings of the 18th of July, we used the TV grab to sample four localities of this rift zone from south to north. These samples, along with samples and observations made during the previous dive in this area suggest that also at São Miguel, the western rift zone merely has been active over the past few thousand years and that the historic and youngest eruptions in the Azores are very small and localised.

The next ROV dive targeted the northern rift zone of Sete Cidades volcano on São Miguel and revealed numerous older lava flows intercalated with volcanoclastic sediments. The ROV imagery displayed no evidence for recent volcanism. The presence of numerous fishing lines limited the radius in which the ROV could move and the dive was aborted in the early evening hours. Upon ascent of the ROV, it became obvious that a large amount of fishing nets had been caught by the ROV cable. Fortunately, these nets and lines could be removed without causing any damage on the equipment. During the night of the 18th to the 19th of July, sampling continued using the TV grab along the northern wall of the Hirondele Basin. The sampling localities had been selected based on their elevated topography and hard reflectors in the backscatter images. The samples consisted of carbonates, coral debris and a single large lava piece from one position. Our sampling did not corroborate reports of an historic eruption in the vicinity of this area.

During the 19th we performed an ROV dive on the southern rift shoulder of the Hironnelle Basin some 20 km west of São Miguel again targeting the older rift shoulder. Twelve samples were collected, revealing abundant lava flows, pillow lavas and possibly also dikes. During the following night, we performed a bathymetric survey towards the East Azores Fracture Zone in the south of the Azores Plateau where the next ROV dive in the morning hours of the 20th was planned to sample an almost 1700 m high cliff-wall exposed along the East Azores Fracture Zone. As a result of technical problems we reached the bottom of the seafloor not before lunchtime. The samples that arrived on deck during the early evening hours unexpectedly turned out to be moderately to highly altered peridotites. During the night, the multibeam survey covered much of the vicinity of the East Azores Fracture Zone before heading to continue the ROV profile during the morning hours of the 21st of July. A technical problem with the ROV's winch however, led to a change in plans and we started sampling the profile using the TV grab. Two very successful TV grabs were used to sample further peridotite outcrops, a third TV grab unfortunately remained empty.

During the night to the 22nd of July we continued a multibeam survey towards the western extension of Princesa Alice bank before another ROV dive was carried out to start upslope sampling of platform building lavas. The dive covered almost 1 km of igneous outcrops revealing numerous dikes and lava flows with patches of sediment in between. The majority of the samples are fine-grained, greenschist-facies, chlorite-bearing samples originating from the sheeted dike complex where the final sample of the dive from 1730 m water depth turned out to be a pillow lava implying that this may be the transition between the sheeted dikes and the pillow lavas from the mid-ocean ridge crust. During the night and the early morning hours of the 23th of July, we sampled the rift zone west of Faial, the young volcanic system of Capelinhos, erupted in 1958-1959. One of four successful TV grabs along Capelinhos brought a series of fishing lines on deck. A short multibeam survey was conducted across the eruption site. We decided against any ROV diving in the vicinity of Capelinhos during this cruise, due to the abundance of fishing lines in mid-water and the threat this posed on safe ROV operations. We instead moved towards Condor de Terra, approximately 10 miles southwest of Faial, where we started diving on a fissural feature that had previously been interpreted as a younger seamount (based on seismic profiles from M113). During the dive on the 23rd of July we observed numerous lava flow outcrops and volcanoclastic rocks interrupted by patches of carbonate sediments. The samples that were brought to the surface turned out to be mostly moderately altered igneous rocks with abundant carbonate vesicle fillings. During the early evening we headed towards the Capelinhos eruption site, where colleagues from the University of Horta in the Azores came alongside with a small vessel to take the refrigerated biological specimen collected back to their University's cooling store. This procedure avoided a lengthy and expensive transport post-cruise. We then continued our work with five TV grab stations covering almost the entire length of the accessible Capelinhos eruption site (~5 km). These samples comprised mostly consolidated, fresh and glassy ash as well as lapilli and lava and pillow fragments. During the early morning hours of the 24th of July we headed towards Princesa Alice bank to continue the stratigraphic profile from the 22nd of July. The profile started at about 2000 m water depth and when the ROV finally reached the surface on the evening of the 24th 13 samples were brought back to the surface. During the night to the 25th of July, we continued a hydroacoustic survey towards the volcanic system of

Capelinhos where we sampled the two northerly rift zones using the TV grab. These samples are mostly carbonate crusts and fine-grained sandy material and reveal that the two rift zones north of Capelinhos are extinct and have not experienced any volcanism in historic times. We then continued with a multibeam survey towards the western coastline of São Jorge and surveyed the western rift system of São Jorge.

On the morning of the 25th of July we then started our 19th and final ROV dive of cruise M128. The imagery and samples revealed that much of the rift structure is covered by large amounts of sediment and carbonates, however, few igneous outcrops were sampled (5 samples). The remaining TV grabs targeted the rift zone west of São Jorge and confirmed that no young volcanic activity occurred along this structure. The geological sampling ended at 2:00 am of the 26th of July and we then started a 370-km long hydroacoustic survey from São Jorge, towards Faial, then north towards Graciosa and along the southern rift shoulder of the Terceira rift axis towards São Miguel.

All scientific measurements ended at 4:00 Wednesday the 27th of July 2016 and we arrived on the pier in Ponta Delgada at 9:00 where the cruise ended.

5 Preliminary Results

5.1 Underway Hydroacoustics

(Blum, M., Petry, F., Bach, W.)

5.1.1 System Overview and interpretation

The bathymetric data were recorded by two swath sounders (Fig. A1). Specifically, the shallow-water Kongsberg multibeam sonar EM710 and the deep-water Kongsberg multibeam sonar EM122 were used depending on the prevailing water depth. The EM122 operates at 12 kHz, whereas the EM710 used in water depths shallower than 700 m operates at 70-100 kHz. The beams are emitted in a swath across the ship's axis achieving a maximum beam tilt angle of 140° (EM710) and 150° (EM122). Routinely, the EM122 swath's opening angle was set to 60°/60° from nadir in water depths >2000 m, while wider angles (e.g., 65° between 2000 and 1000 mbsl, and 70° <1000 mbsl) were used in shallower water depths. Each swath consists of 400/432 beams resulting in a footprint's width of up to 30 km (depending on water depth and angle) and a horizontal resolution of approximately 2% of the water depth.

Multibeam profiles during M128 were recorded focusing on the western rim of São Miguel, João de Castro, Serreta, Pico Ridge and the East Azores Fracture Zone in the south. The total distance of sampled Multi-beam data sums up to for 1980 km (1100 nm. see Fig. A1, Appendix).

The data reveal two dominant volcanic ridges towards NW and N, as well as a less developed ridge NNE of João de Castro. A feature that previously appeared as crater SE of João de Castro was identified as an artefact from earlier expeditions. Instead of a crater the new bathymetric

data identify a well-developed ridge. The mapping SW of São Miguel towards the EAFZ with the EM122 system, allowed us to eliminate a strong bathymetric artefact in the ETOPO dataset starting in Ponta Delgada and heading southwest towards South America. The new dataset from the East Azores Fracture Zone brought new insights into the southern border between the Azores Plateau and the basin towards the south. In the areas of the western rifts of the islands of Terceira, Faial, São Miguel, and São Jorge, multibeam surveys were conducted to produce high-resolution bathymetry to be used for the subsequent ROV dives and TV grabs.

The bathymetry data were gridded mainly to 20 m resolution using MB-systems software and relayed to the ROV team in order for the science party to have a proper bathymetry reference frame during the dives. Many of the bathymetry and backscatter details revealed in these maps were used to select targets for ROV dives and TV-grab stations. The details of the seafloor geology and petrology at these sites are presented in sections 5.3 of this report. From a seafloor bathymetry point of view, a number of observations are noteworthy: The data recovered at Pico Ridge showed several cone shaped structures which were not known from previous data. Also, at the western rift of São Miguel a very slow multibeam profile was performed as close to the island as possible without getting into environmentally protected area. Several volcanic cones and ridges west of Faial showed up in much greater details than in previously existing bathymetry data. The detailed EM710 bathymetry data collected in the Serreta area, west of Terceira, was of cornerstone importance in planning the ROV dives in that area. The bathymetry data revealed that the southernmost rim of what could have been interpreted as a succession of volcanic craters was indeed a neovolcanic rift and the site of the most recent eruptions west of Terceira (see section 5.4 for more details).

Water column data were recorded from all surveys over apparently young volcanic rifts (e.g. Serreta, Capelinhos, etc.). The data were screened with the Midwater module of the Fledermaus suite of programs to detect gas flares due to volcanic degassing in the water column. The data revealed the presence of occasional irregular-shaped bodies of high reflectivity. These bodies did not have the near-vertical, elongate shapes of gas flare-related anomalies. A reconnaissance survey during the first dive on João de Castro seamount revealed the occurrence of fish swarms and a lack of gas flares in an area where such anomalies were detected during a preceding echo sounder survey. None of the water columns surveys conducted in the course of M128 yielded any indication of the presence of gas flares.

5.2 Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) Quest 4000

(V. Ratmeyer, A. Kausche, T. Leymann, H. A. Mai, T. Schade, M. Schröder, V. Vittori, G. Wefer,)

The deepwater remotely operated vehicle (ROV) “QUEST 4000m” used during M128 aboard the RV METEOR, is based and operated at MARUM, Center for Marine Environmental Sciences at the University of Bremen, Germany. The QUEST ROV is based on a commercially available 4000 m rated deepwater robotic vehicle designed and built by Schilling Robotics, Davis, USA. Since installation at MARUM in May 2003, it was designed as a truly mobile system specifically adapted to the requirements of scientific work aboard marine research vessels for worldwide

operation. Today, QUEST has a total record of 407 dives during 35 expeditions, including this cruise, M128 Azores Plateau. During M128, QUEST performed 19 dives to depths between 270 m and 2800 m. Tasks included rock sampling and biological sampling, as well as high quality photographic and video documentation. A challenge during the entire cruise was the operation along very steep underwater slopes with hundreds of meters elevation, demanding a close cooperation between precise vessel navigation and ROV operation. In addition, the proximity to the Azores islands induced a risk of fishing line encounters, which happened 3 times at the shallower sites, luckily without any hurt or damage.

QUEST was operated by a team of 8 pilots/technicians. Close cooperation between ROV team and ship's crew on deck and bridge allowed a safe and routinely performed handling procedures during deployment and recovery. During diving, close cooperation allowed excellent positioning and navigation of both ship and ROV at depth, which was essential for accurate sampling and safe underwater operation in such demanding morphology.

QUEST System description

The total QUEST system weighs about 45 tons (including the vehicle, control van, workshop van, electrical winch, 5000 m umbilical, and transportation vans) and can be transported in four standard ISO 20 foot vans. Using a MacArtney Cormac electrically driven storage winch to manage the 5000m of 17.6 mm NSW umbilical, no hydraulic connections are necessary to host the entire handling system.

The QUEST uses a Doppler velocity log (DVL, 1200kHz) to perform stationkeep, displacement, and other auto control functions. The combination of 60-kW propulsion power with DVL-based auto control functions provides exceptional positioning capabilities at depth. Designed and operated as a free-flying vehicle, QUEST system exerts such precise control over the electric propulsion system that the vehicle could maintain relative positioning hold within decimeters. Absolute GPS-based positioning is carried out using the shipboard IXSEA POSIDONIA USBL positioning system.

The QUEST control system provides transparent access to all RS-232, network data and video channels. The scientific data system used at MARUM feeds all ROV- and ship-based science and logging channels into a real-time database system (DAVIS-ROV), a version of the database software commonly used aboard the German research vessels. During operation, data such as the Sonar screen, DVL map and so forth plus most videos video including the HD feed are distributed to the lab and ships Ethernet network in real-time to minimize crowding in the control van.

Post-cruise data archival will be hosted by the information system PANGAEA at the World Data Center for Marine Environmental Sciences (WDC-MARE), which is operated on a long-term base by MARUM and the Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven (AWI).

QUEST Video Setup and HDTV camera

Continuous PAL SD video footage was obtained with two colour-zoom cameras (INSITE PEGASUS). In order to gain a fast overview of the dive without the need of watching hours of video, the videos are frame-grabbed and digitized at 5 sec intervals, covering both PAL and HD video material. For extremely detailed video close up filming, a near-bottom mounted broadcast quality (>1000 TVL) 3CCD HDTV 14 x Zoom video camera was used (INSITE ZEUS). Spatial Resolution of this camera is 2.2 Mega-Pixel at 59.94 Hz interlaced. Recording was carried out on demand onto tapes in broadcast-standard digital Sony HD-CAM format, using uncompressed 1.5 Gbit HD-SDI transmission over a dedicated fibre-optic connection. In addition, all video feeds were continuously recorded digitally based on H.264 compression, including HDTV and tiled pilot screen, and were transferred as digital files to the ships science server between dives. The files cover 30 minutes of video each for faster and easier access and contain a separate subtitle text-file with relevant vehicle data such as position, heading, depth and timestamp.

As a standard photo camera, an INSITE SCORPIO DIGITAL STILL camera was used, providing 3.3 Mega-Pixel spatial image resolution and highly corrected underwater optics. For mosaicking and vertical downward view, a 24 Mega-Pixel digital photographic camera with two vertical external flashes was installed. Video distribution was provided by dedicated CAT-6 based DVI transmission hardware, as well as by streaming the main tiled video image into the vessels network. Scientists were able to take part in the dives from a dedicated media setup in the vessels universal lab, whereas the scientific dive leader and a second scientist could participate inside the control van.

Scientific payloads

During M128, the following scientific equipment was handled with QUEST:

ROV based tools, installed on vehicle:

- 2 hydraulic manipulators for rock sampling
- nets with t-handles
- ROV starboardside fixed basket frame
- shovels with t-handle for digging up sediment
- T-Lance with logger

List of QUEST dives during M128

No.	Dive No.	Date	Site		Depth (m)	Bottom Time	Total Dive Time	Bottom hours	Total Dive hours	
1	389	04.07.2016	38° 12.57' N	026° 34.59' W	270	09:00	09:48	9.00	9.80	
2	390	05.07.2016	38° 22.75' N	026° 33.29' W	2549	07:41	11:23	7.68	11.38	
3	391	06.07.2016	38° 15.39' N	026° 36.76' W	900	08:29	10:36	8.48	10.60	
4	392	07.07.2016	38° 49.08' N	027° 28.54' W	611	06:16	07:40	6.27	7.67	
5	393	08.07.2016	38° 23.27' N	027° 55.51' W	482	04:15	05:32	4.25	5.53	
6	394	09.07.2016	39° 01.46' N	027° 30.76' W	1647	09:43	12:10	9.72	12.17	
7	395	10.07.2016	38° 47.49' N	027° 28.07' W	326	10:53	11:44	10.88	11.73	
8	396	11.07.2016	38° 47.46' N	027° 28.05' W	328	07:38	08:33	7.63	8.55	
9	397	12.07.2016	38° 46.90' N	027° 27.53' W	456	07:28	09:21	7.47	9.35	
10	398	14.07.2016	39° 06.95' N	028° 11.42' W	671	10:20	11:33	10.33	11.55	
11	399	15.07.2016	38° 23.27' N	026° 32.64' W	1983	08:29	11:24	8.48	11.40	
12	400	17.07.2016	37° 53.45' N	025° 55.10' W	400	04:22	05:31	4.37	5.52	
13	401	18.07.2016	37° 55.86' N	025° 51.53' W	753	09:19	10:53	9.32	10.88	
14	402	19.07.2016	37° 49.70' N	026° 04.41' W	2256	06:50	10:24	6.83	10.40	
15	403	20.07.2016	36° 51.58' N	027° 25.67' W	2789	06:15	10:21	6.25	10.35	
16	404	22.07.2016	38° 11.81' N	029° 33.88' W	2553	08:20	11:58	8.33	11.97	
17	405	23.07.2016	38° 34.43' N	029° 06.80' W	940	09:15	10:06	9.25	10.10	
18	406	24.07.2016	38° 12.01' N	029° 33.57' W	1989	08:30	11:35	8.50	11.58	
19	407	25.07.2016	38° 47.05' N	028° 27.59' W	953	08:51	11:20	8.85	11.33	
					Max. Dive depth (m):	2789	7.99	Total hours:	151.90	191.87

Table 5.1: Positions and Times of M128 QUEST dives**5.3 Petrology**

(Beier, C., Bach, W., Ferreira, P., Genske, F.S., Haase, K.M., Kemner, F., Klügel, A., Krumm, S., Kueppers, U., Romer, R., Skambraks, T., Schleifer, B., Storch, B.)

5.3.1. Sampling and analytical methods

Igneous and sedimentary and biological samples during M128 were taken with the Remotely Operated Vehicle, (ROV QUEST 4000) of the MARUM-ZENTRUM FÜR MARINE UMWELTWISSENSCHAFTEN in Bremen and with a video-guided grab from GEOMAR

HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR OZEANFORSCHUNG, Kiel operated on winch W12 on RV METEOR. Sampling with the ROV (see Appendix 2 for ROV descriptions) and the TV grab was based on hydroacoustic (see section 5.1) and visual observations made before and during the individual dives. Preferentially, areas were targeted that had given previous, bathymetric and seismic (from M113) evidence for solid, igneous rock occurrences (see Appendix 3 for sample descriptions). Samples were described on board and packed for petrological and geochemical analyses at the GeoZentrum Nordbayern, Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg.

5.3.2. Preliminary results, petrological observations and interpretations

The sampling strategy by TV grab and ROV QUEST 4000 was adjusted to the hydroacoustic survey observations on a daily basis. ROV dive and TV grab localities were defined based on their shape and topography as well as on backscatter images revealing hard and soft reflectors. The preliminary results will be based on the different sampling localities reflecting the older (East Azores Fracture Zone, Hirondele Basin) and younger (João de Castro, Serreta, Sete Cidades, Capelinhos, Fig. A2) localities, respectively. During the entire cruise we performed 19 ROV dives (217 rock samples), 70 TV grabs (118 samples), 1980 km of hydroacoustic surveying and obtained a total of more than 330 samples covering these areas. Here, we will describe the different sampling regions based on their geological implications, i.e. we have separated the description into the younger volcanic edifices closer to the islands and the submarine seamounts and those localities that consisted of stratigraphic profiles targeting the older plateau-building stage.

Younger volcanic edifices

The younger and in part historically active extensions west of the islands and the seamount João de Castro were preferentially targeted within a distance of 20 km of the main volcanic edifice. The dives were performed in areas where the hydroacoustic surveys revealed rift zone structures and the backscatter images display both soft and hard reflectors.

João de Castro

The submarine seamount of João de Castro (Fig. 5.1, Fig. A2) has been a major target during cruise M128. We performed two ROV dives (732-ROV, 745-ROV) and a total of 17 successful TV grabs at central João de Castro, the western (~striking 304°) and northwestern rift zones (~striking 329°) cutting through the seamount. The new EM 710 hydroacoustic data revealed that the seamount consists of numerous smaller volcanic edifices along these rift zones. Dive 732-ROV targeted the immediate vicinity of the hydrothermal vent site previously described by Cardigos et al. (2005). However, the samples and ROV imagery did not indicate any evidence that this area of the seamount has previously been hydrothermally active. Our sampling at João de Castro also showed that the western rift zone cutting the seamount (sampled by TV grabs, e.g., 735-TVG and 737-TVG) is covered by coral debris, carbonates and variably altered volcanic material implying that this rift zone has not been active historically. In contrast, samples from the northern rift zone and the eastern part of João de Castro seamount (e.g., 740-TVG, 741-

Fig. 5.1: Sampling localities and results from the hydroacoustic surveys at João de Castro seamount.

TVG, 743-TVG, 732-ROV) indicated that the youngest volcanism may be focussed towards the crater and a 12 km-long rift zone cutting the eastern part of the seamount. The different directions of the rift systems and their different ages suggested that magmatism and tectonic activity in the Azores may have changed systematically in the past and dating of these samples could reveal when a change in tectonic direction in the Azores occurred.

Serreta and west of Terceira

The Serreta flank eruption from 1998-2001 was evident from lava balloons rising to the sea surface and floating for several hours before sinking back to the ocean floor (Casalbore et al., 2015; Gaspar et al., 2003; Kueppers et al., 2012). However, to date no extensive hydroacoustic or sampling survey had been performed at the eruption site. Four successful dives (751-ROV, 767-ROV, 774-ROV and 781-ROV) and 15 TV grab stations were performed in the vicinity of Serreta ridge (Fig. 5.2, Fig. A2) and revealed the size and structure of the eruption vent. Most samples from the 1998-2001 rift zones are fresh and glassy lavas (767-ROV, 774-ROV and 781-ROV). In the central area of the volcano several hydroacoustic surveys and rock sampling imply that the most recent activity at Serreta occurred along a 3.7 km East-West striking, 300 m wide ridge. The sampling also indicated that the most recent eruption likely occurred along the southern rather than the northern rift zone of Serreta. The dive imagery provided evidence for previous hydrothermal activity in the form of sulphur precipitations and bacterial mats. However, we did not find unambiguous evidence for the presence of recent hydrothermal vent fields, e.g., by the presence of shimmering water or temperature anomalies. Two additional TV grabs (749-TVG and 753-TVG) and dive 751-ROV (12 samples) contained fresh pillow lavas

Fig. 5.2: Sampling localities and results from the hydroacoustic surveys at Serreta, west of the island of Terceira.

along with altered scoriaceous rocks that may not be related to the 1998-2001 eruption. In addition, a single TV grab (782-TVG) along the northern part of the rift through Terceira contained a single small altered lava fragment. Our observations suggest that the youngest volcanism west of Terceira is focussed at the vicinity of the Serreta fissure while the northern rift system of Terceira has not experienced recent volcanism.

Pico Ridge

Sampling at Pico Ridge targeted an area, in which the submarine ridge changes in strike from 283° in the west to 314° along the eastern part of this feature. A single ROV dive (755-ROV) and six TV grabs (756-TVG to 761-TVG) covered the area, in which the change in direction occurs along the ridge. The TV-grabs usually contained strongly altered, volcanoclastic breccias and carbonate rocks, only 760-TVG also recovered a few small basaltic rock fragments. The dive showed that the majority of the outcrops consist of carbonate-cemented breccia and only occasionally altered lavas. We did not find any evidence in this area that, despite the close spatial presence of recent and historic volcanism at Pico island some 20 km away, recent volcanism affected any of the Pico Ridge seamounts. This observation is in agreement with an age of 1.49 Ma determined on a dredge sample from this area (Beier et al., 2015).

Graciosa

The ROV sampling (787-ROV) and hydroacoustic surveys west of Graciosa imply that the rift zone northwest of the island has not been active historically as inferred from the altered basalt samples, several strongly altered samples of volcanoclastic breccias as well as thick carbonate and sand covers on top of the volcanic rocks. In addition, the sampling and the hydroacoustic imagery suggest that rifting west of Graciosa may largely be amagmatic and continuously transgressing into the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. The plate boundary between the Eurasian and African plates west of Graciosa consists of a structural setting in which N-S trending ridges, reflecting the structures found along the ridge axis are, are separated by smaller basin-like structures that strike NW-SE parallel to the recent structural directions found along the Terceira Rift axis.

Sete Cidades at São Miguel

The sampling of the rift zone west of São Miguel (Fig. 5.3, Fig. A2) was aimed at determining whether any of the rift zones close to São Miguel reveal evidence for young volcanism similar to that observed at the subaerial edifice at Sete Cidades (Beier et al., 2006; Cole et al., 2008; Pacheco et al., 2005; Queiroz et al., 2008; Renzulli and Santi, 2000). Two ROV dives (791-ROV, 796-ROV) and 6 TV grabs (717-TVG, 718-TVG, 792-TVG to 795-TVG) west of Sete Cidades did not show convincing evidence for historic volcanism. However, the presence of glassy pillow rims (717-TVG, 718-TVG) and relatively fresh pyroclastic samples (793-TVG) implies relatively young volcanism in both, the northern and southern rift zones of Sete Cidades

Fig. 5.3: Dive localities and TV grab stations in the two respective rift zones west of Sete Cidades volcano, São Miguel.

volcano, extending up to 8 km from the shoreline and some 10 km from the main volcanic system. These samples, along with results from previous cruises (Pos232, 286 and M113; (Hübscher et al., 2016)) imply that the youngest submarine volcanism in this area may be focussed towards the western rift zones of São Miguel.

Faial and Condor de Terra

The submarine extension of the Capelinhos eruption that occurred in 1958-1959 is the first historically documented eruption during which a submarine eruption approached and rose above the sea surface (Cole et al., 2001; Coutinho et al., 2010). Our initial aim was to have several ROV dives in the vicinity of Capelinhos; however, as a result of a fishing net being caught in 813-TVG we decided to cancel the ROV dives at Capelinhos and the volcanic system was instead intensively sampled by 10 TV grabs (811-TVG to 815-TVG and 818-TVG to 822-TVG) covering almost 5 km of the eruption site. We mostly found consolidated ash layers and glassy lapilli along with fresh, glassy lavas and pillow fragments all indicating that the Capelinhos eruption site extends some 8 km westward from the recent coastline and has a width of up to 4 km in a N-S direction. The majority of the rocks found at Capelinhos are pyroclastic in nature implying that many of the earlier volcanic edifices, and potentially also lava flows, have been covered by the products of the Surtseyan 1958-1959 eruptions. The rocks here are clearly distinct from those erupted along the Serreta fissure that generally display more pyroclastic characteristics. Both localities, imply that their melts were volatile-rich in agreement with the idea of a volatile-rich nature of the upper mantle underneath the Azores.

ROV dive (817-TVG) 18 km southwest of Capelinhos at Condor de Terra showed several lava flows with scattered carbonate sediments and volcanoclastic material. The samples from these lava flows are moderately to strongly altered mafic igneous rocks with calcite vesicle fillings, implying that the youngest magmatic activity close to Faial may be restricted to Capelinhos and does not extend southward. The overall implications from our observations is that the islands of Faial and Pico may be the southern border of the younger volcanic activity in the Azores and that the outcrops of Princesa Alice bank and Condor de Terra belong to the older magmatic stages related to plateau formation.

São Jorge

The final ROV dive (829-ROV) west of São Jorge covered almost 400 m of elevation and exhibited old seafloor encrusted by carbonate with only occasional igneous rock outcrops. Five TV grabs along the rift system west of São Jorge and the hydroacoustic profiles imply that there is no evidence for young volcanic or tectonic activity along the western submarine ridge of São Jorge. These findings indicate that volcanic activity in this area has been extinct for a significant period of time which is in agreement with the relatively old age of 1.3 to 0.68 Ma of the subaerial volcanism (Hildenbrand et al., 2008). Combined with the observation that volcanism at Graciosa seems to have ceased at or even before the Terceira Rift was active implies that in fact the only western edifice that is still active at the western border of the Azores Plateau is Faial.

Stratigraphic profiles and edifices of the early platform building stages

We had selected four localities at which we wanted to dive with the ROV and use the TV grab to sample the earlier, plateau-building volcanic stages of the Azores Plateau. These were sampled in the Hirondele Basin, i.e. north of João de Castro (dives 738-ROV and 789-ROV) and south of São Miguel (802-ROV), northwest of Terceira (764-ROV), along the East Azores Fracture Zone (804-ROV, 806-TVG and 807-TVG) and at Princesa Alice Bank (810-ROV, 824-ROV). The samples cover a wide range of rock samples from altered ultramafic rocks along the East Azores Fracture Zone, to greenschist-facies and zeolite-facies altered dikes and pillow lavas at Princesa Alice Bank to pillow lavas and lava flows at the Terceira Rift profiles. During the dives particular care was taken to sample only outcrops on the walls, i.e. rocks that were in situ rather than talus fans and debris. Only in some cases sampling of talus could not be avoided.

Hirondele Basin and north of Terceira

Dive 802-ROV along the southern cliff of the Hirondele Basin (Fig. A3) yielded ten igneous rock samples, ranging from fresh and glassy to slightly altered lavas that will be compared to the older lavas of the stratigraphic section further north (738-ROV and 789-ROV, Fig. 5.4).

Fig. 5.4: Elevation profile of 738-ROV and 780-ROV. Please note that the topographic irregularities at the lower end of the profile are due to artefacts in the bathymetric data. Numbers correspond to sampling localities of the two dives.

The absence of fauna in most parts of the profile may indicate recent tectonic activity in this area. The samples of the northern profile comprised basalts with columnar jointing and sheeted dikes in the lower part of the profile transgressing into pillow lavas in the upper part of the profile. The 22 samples from the upper part of the profile from 1935 to 1308 m were mostly fresh to moderately altered pillow lavas and lava flows. The top of the entire profile was reached at 1279 m water depth where the outcrop changed into a relatively flat area of sand and carbonates. The stratigraphic profile (764-ROV) along the northern rift shoulder of the basin west of Terceira, however, were more pervasively altered than samples in the other stratigraphic profiles of the Terceira rift system.

We suggest that all three profile sections of the Hirondele Basin originate from the rifting of the ultraslow spreading Terceira rift axis and may represent the older stages of the submarine Azores Plateau, albeit younger and further up in the stratigraphy of the Azores than the samples from the East Azores Fracture Zone and the Princesa Alice Bank.

East Azores Fracture Zone

We had selected the sampling locality along the East Azores Fracture Zone (804-ROV and 806-TVG and 807-TVG) based on hydroacoustic and seismic data from M113 (Hübscher et al., 2016). These outcrops were targeted for the ROV dives to obtain a stratigraphic profile from the early potentially tholeiitic plateau-building stage to the later alkaline eruptions. The seven ROV samples and nine samples from the two TV grabs are exclusively serpentinised and highly altered peridotites, which commonly occur along fracture zones of mid-ocean ridges. However, the samples were taken from about 1200 m above the surrounding seafloor implying a large vertical offset along the East Azores Fracture Zone. In addition, we tentatively interpret these ultramafic lithologies as being part of the normal oceanic crust formed at the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. We did not find any evidence for the occurrence of mafic or extrusive rocks in the ROV dive and the TV grabs. The rocks found along the East Azores Fracture Zone thus represent the deepest lithology sampled during M128.

Princesa Alice Bank

The stratigraphic profile sampled by two dives (810-ROV and 824-ROV) at the western Princesa Alice Bank covers almost 1.5 kilometres of igneous rock outcrops. The 12 samples from the deeper part of the profile (2448-1713 m water depth) are mostly greenschist-facies aphanitic rocks that likely originated from the sheeted dike section. Altered pillow lava was recovered at about 1800 m depth (810ROV-11) which may indicate that we have reached the dike-pillow lava transition. The continuation of this profile with 824-ROV showed that the overlying lava flows are also heavily altered aphyric lavas and dikes with zeolite, clay, and carbonate vein fillings.

5.4 Volcanology

(Kueppers, U., Beier, C.)

During the cruise and along with the igneous samples we also sampled and mapped volcanoclastic deposits using the ROV QUEST and TV grab. We sampled volcanoclastic deposits at João do Castro (erupted in 1720), Capelinhos (1957/58) and Serreta (1998-2001). The volcanic eruptions observed during cruise M128 are either extrusive or very shallow intrusive resulting in basaltic lava, commonly dense, sometimes vesicular (containing dikes, lava flows and pillow lava with chilled glassy margins). In supposedly proximal deposits of basaltic explosive eruptions we commonly observed highly vesicular clasts, with strong bubble size gradients and with micro-porous chilled margin, still glassy. These are sometimes slab-shaped, bound by brittle fractures. These samples also contain variable phenocryst contents of olivine, clinopyroxene and plagioclase. The slab-shaped clasts particularly observed at Serreta may be fragments of lava balloons (767-ROV, 774-ROV and 781-ROV). The subaerial pendants of these lava balloons likely are pyroclastic ejecta such as scoriaceous bombs and spatter. At Serreta we also found irregular clasts containing large (up to dm) and frequently convoluted gas pockets, bound by a few cm-thick layer of basaltic lava with strong bubble gradients towards the rim (771-TVG, 772-TVG) and variable phenocryst contents (Ol, Cpx, Plag). We also found comparable samples at João do Castro (728-TVG). A subaerial equivalent for these clasts is, to date, not known.

Based on the sampling and hydroacoustic data we suggest that the 1998-2001 eruption of Serreta started from a single fissure in the western part. In the central area, this fissure splits into two parallel fissures, which are enclosing two more N-S trending fissures in the eastern part. The initial hypothesis that Serreta is composed of a crater system had to be changed during M128 as the hydroacoustic data image a combined system of laterally elongated fissures and a volcanic ridge in the northern part.

The volcanoclastic deposits formed from the explosive eruptions consist of mm- to cm-thick layers of primarily medium- to coarse-grained volcanic ash. These were sampled at Capelinhos (811-TVG, 812-TVG, 819-TVG, 821-TVG), João de Castro (732-ROV, 743-TVG, 741-TVG, 746-TVG), Serreta (767-ROV, 774-ROV and 781-ROV) and Sete Cidades (793-TVG). Ash layers of constant thickness covering clasts of few dm are interpreted to represent the settling from an oversaturated suspension. Some layers exhibit primary thickness variations caused by differential deposition from overloaded density currents (e.g., 746-TVG, 812-TVG). As both layer types alternate without fine-ash layers or signs of bioturbation or colonisation, these facies are interpreted as a primary deposit without significant (if at all) contribution from reworking. The subaerial equivalent of these eruptions would be fall deposits and deposits from pyroclastic density currents.

5.5 Biology

(Sampaio, Í., Cerqueira, T.)

5.5.1 Materials and Methods

Video Annotation of Biology

During the ROV dives at the Azores plateau, video annotation of the observed biology was carried out. Most taxa were identified to the Filo level but deep-sea octocorals were identified to the genus or species level taking into account the expertise of the biologists on-board.

Biological Sampling

Biological samples of macrobenthonic invertebrates were caught by TV grab or the ROV MARUM QUEST during M128. While samples collected with TV grabs were not previously selected, the biological samples collected by ROV were previously observed in video and selected as priority samples. Geological samples with biological epibiont species were also sampled. Samples of macroinvertebrates like sponges, crustacea, polychaeta, bryozoa and hydrozoa were predominantly preserved in ethanol 70% or 96%. Deep-sea corals were preserved in ethanol 100% and 70% and formaldehyde 10% on board for morphological and genetic studies.

5.5.2 Preliminary results, biological observations and interpretations

Deep-Sea fauna of the Azores

After the scientific campaigns of Prince Albert I of Monaco to the Azores in the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, M128 represents the scientific cruise that recorded the biggest geographical and vertical area of the deep-sea fauna in the Azores by the use of modern methodological technologies. During the dives of the ROV MARUM QUEST 4000, deep-sea and coastal fishes like *Pagellus bogaraveo*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Anthias anthias* and *Capros aper* were commonly recorded. Schools were registered comprised by the species *Anthias anthias* and *Capros aper* (Fig. 5.5a). Several deep-sea shark species were also filmed during this cruise.

Macrobenthonic invertebrates were observed during the ROV dives or collected by the TV grab. Deep-sea corals and sponges were the predominant macroinvertebrates recognised in video and/or being sampled. Nonetheless, hydrozoans, bryozoans, crustaceans and molluscs were often observed during the 19 dives of the ROV MARUM QUEST and the TV grabs. Sponges (Porifera) were more abundant at older locations where carbonates were the main substrate as observed in Pico and São Jorge ridges (see also section 5.3). At some localities they were also observed forming sponge grounds of great extension (Fig. 5.5b). However, locations where the substrate is apparently more recent seem to be colonised by both sponges and corals, being the last more common. Among the deep-sea corals inhabiting the Azores archipelago, the deep-sea octocorals (Octocorallia: Alcyonacea) were the most abundant and diverse.

Insights on the Coral fauna of the Azores

Some species of deep-sea corals already known to occur in the Azores (Braga-Henriques et al., 2013) revealed to be widespread through the Azores plateau: the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*, the plexaurid *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor*, *Acanthogorgia armata*, the alcyoniids *Pseudoanthomastus agaricus* and *Alcyonium rubrum* and the black coral *Sticopathes gravieri*.

Within the Octocorallia, the family Plexauridae was the most representative in terms of species richness and abundance during most ROV dives. The plexaurid *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor* is structurally important on a coral garden previously described for Condor seamount (Tempera et al., 2012).

Fig. 5.5: Biological records from the cruise M128: a) School of *Capros aper*, b) Sponge ground, c) coral garden of *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor*, d) biggest colony of *Acanthogorgia armata* from young area of Serreta; e) *Paromola cuvieri* carrying-behaviour upside down with Porifera; f) potential reef of *Eguchipsammia* sp. Figures a, b, c, e are copyright of MARUM – Zentrum für Marine Umweltwissenschaften.

During M128 two coral gardens where this species is predominant were filmed: Serreta (dive 395/767-ROV) and the west flank of S. Miguel (dive 400/791-ROV) (Fig. 5.5c). Several other species of Plexauridae were also observed, recorded and sampled whenever possible. Nonetheless, their identification through ROV videos is extremely difficult or even impossible. Further electron microscopy and genetic work will reveal the identity of most of plexaurid species in the future.

Corallidae is other family of octocorals that is represented by three species in the northeastern Atlantic Ocean (Sampaio et al., 2009). *Corallium johnsoni* is known to occur in the Azores since 2009 and, consequently, more records of this species were expected for the upcoming years. A coral garden formed by this species was recorded during the ROV dive 401 (796-ROV) west of São Miguel. Additionally, a TV grab in Capelinhos, Faial brought some specimens of an unknown species of *Corallium*. This specimens most likely represent a new species for the scientific records.

Other species recorded forming coral gardens were the octocorals *Viminella flagellum* and *Acanthogorgia armata* in association with *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor* through huge extensions off the west flank of São Miguel and Serreta. Also at Serreta, fresh lavas that most likely have their origin from the last eruption of 1998-2001, were colonised by two species of octocorals *Acanthogorgia armata* and *Swiftia dubia*. In 2011 during the cruise FAIVI these findings were registered based on dredged samples (Chiocci et al., 2011). ROV samples of *Acanthogorgia armata* from Serreta had a maximum length of about 10 cm (Fig. 5.5d). If the settlement of the lavas occurred near the date of the eruption, it can indicate a growth rate of about 0,55cm/year for this species.

At João de Castro (dive 390/738-ROV), Hirondele Basin (dive 399/789-ROV), East Azores Fracture Zone (dive 402/802-ROV) and Princesa Alice (dive 403/804ROV) the deepest dives took place between 1270 m and 2786 m (see section 5.2) revealing less abundance of octocorals, as expected. Predominant are species from the family of the bamboo corals Isididae, e.g., *Acanella arbuscula*. Chrysogorgiidae, Plexauridae and the primnoid *Candidella imbricata* were also present and common during the deepest ROV dives with some sightings of the black coral *Leiopathes* cf. *glaberrima*. Deepest dives were also where the chrysogorgiid *Metallogorgia melanotrichos* with its associated ophiuroid living within its polyps. Several taxa are in strict association with deep-sea octocorals as is the case of the carrying-behaviour of the spider-crab *Paromola cuvieri* with sponges and octocorals (Braga-Henriques et al., 2012). However, the purpose of this behaviour is still unknown. A great number of specimens of *Paromola cuvieri* were filmed carrying sponges, octocorals and black corals. Two of the specimens were filmed still and upside down on rocks with the carrying species turned upwards to the water column. Hiding from predators seems to be the motif of this carrying-behaviour (Fig. 5.5e).

Deep-sea reefs composed by Scleractinian corals as known from Norway fjords were never found in the Azores. Nonetheless, the same coral-reef building species inhabit the archipelago sparsely distributed. Coral rubble composed by some species like *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata* was filmed, sometimes, amongst vast areas. This fact may indicate that

previous deep-sea reefs inhabited the Azores in previous times. Recently, a different scleractinian species was found forming a coral reef near Faial island during a submarine LULA500 dive (Tempera et al., 2015). In Pico Ridge 757-TVG captured what seems to be part of a coral reef of the same species *Eguchipsammia* at 309 m (Fig. 5.5f).

However, further analyses must be done in order to complete this results. Samples are essential for the development of taxonomic inventories, the habit mapping of biotopes of the Azores and other scientific studies. During M128 a total of 435 samples of macrobenthos were collected, being 212 samples collected by TV grabs between 146 m and 2395 m and a total of 223 samples collected by ROV dives between 214 m and 2743 m (see Appendix 3, 4 and 5).

5.6 Hydrothermal plume detection by MAPRs

(Klügel, A., Skambraks, T.)

Hydrothermal fluids discharged from venting sites rise buoyantly and expand by incorporation of seawater. The rising hydrothermal plume eventually reaches a neutral buoyancy layer, where it spreads laterally and is carried away by ocean currents. Such plumes or effluent layers have distinctive hydrographic, optical and chemical characteristics, and can be located by tracing respective anomalies in the water column. For this purpose a set of MAPRs (Miniature Autonomous Plume Recorders) was used during cruise M128. The MAPRs were built by the Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL), Seattle, and are housed in an 8.1 cm diameter and 33.4 cm long titanium tube with a protection cap. Each MAPR contains the following probes: 1) A pressure gauge with a range of 0-400 bars and a resolution of 0.013 bars to record the water depth. 2) A thermistor with a resolution of 0.001°C mounted in a titanium probe. 3) A light back scattering sensor (LBSS, or "nephelometer") that senses scattered light from a small volume within centimeters of the sensor window. This is a relative rather than absolute measure of the light backscattering coefficient and provides output data in volts. 4) An oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) sensor. MAPRs are commonly attached to a wire that holds an operating devices such as dredge, CTD or TV grab, or to a wire periodically lifted and lowered during a ship track (tow-yo). The data are logged during the employment and are transferred to a computer after recovery.

Fig. 5.6: Temperature, turbidity and ORP versus pressure of a none-plume influenced profile in the Azores.

During M128 we deployed MAPRs during 15 TV grab stations: at João de Castro seamount (stations 725-TVG, 727-TVG, 733-TVG to 737-TVG, 740-TVG); at a ridge near this seamount (746-TVG); near the Serreta eruptive site west of Terceira (749-TVG, 782-TVG, 783-TVG); at a ridge northwest of Terceira (752-TVG, 753-TVG); and at Pico Ridge (761-TVG). The MAPR was attached to the wire ca. 50 m above the grab (for two stations a second MAPR was attached 50 m above the first), and sample intervals were set to 5 seconds. All MAPR deployments successfully recorded temperature, turbidity and ORP versus pressure (Fig. 5.6), but none yielded any indicator for a hydrothermal plume signal in the water column. Typically, temperatures decreased from around 21 °C at the surface to 14 °C at around 100 m depth, below which the gradient decreased. Turbidity and ORP showed strong variations in the upper 50-100 m of the water column but no systematic deviations below this depth, with turbidity varying by less than 0.01 V in most cases. This result is consistent with the observations during the ROV dives where no indicator for active hydrothermal venting was found.

5.7 Expected Results

(C. Beier, Shipboard Scientific Party)

The hydroacoustic survey data (Fig. A1) will be corrected and will be combined with those from cruises M79 and M113. The final mapped file from these cruises will provide detailed information on the tectonic and volcanic features that form the youngest magmatic edifices of the Azores Plateau. The combined bathymetric and petrological data will show that the majority of the younger volcanism occurs extremely localised on the scale of few 100 meters and along the structural features formed by the ultraslow spreading Terceira Rift. The imagery and sampling from M128 suggests that numerous extensional rift systems in the Azores may be amagmatic and that some submarine volcanic rift zones are extinct. The hydroacoustic survey towards the Mid-Atlantic Ridge reveals that the plate triple junction between the Eurasian and African Plates mostly consists of N-S trending structures from the ridge axis and interrupted by NW-SE trending structural basins parallel to those structures observed along the recent Terceira rift axis. The diagonal basins probably reflect shearing accompanying the ultraslow spreading of the Terceira Rift. We expect these results to be incorporated into a tectonic model of this region revealing more detailed information on the actual site of the plate boundary.

The biological specimens of Plexauridae collected and recorded on video by ROV MARUM QUEST will be studied during the PhD thesis of Íris Sampaio (participating in this cruise) dealing with the taxonomy and biogeography of deep-sea octocorals from the Northeast Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. The specimens of *Corallium* sampled at Capelinhos may be described as a new species for science. Other, yet unidentified species can potentially be new species as well. The ROV imagery collected during 19 dives will contribute to the catalogue of deep-sea marine biotopes developed by Fernando Tempera. All biological samples collected during this cruise will be deposited at COLETA, the biological reference collection of the Department of Oceanography and Fisheries of the University of the Azores (DOP-UAç). Scientists can request the samples and collaborate in future biodiversity studies.

The petrological samples will be used to better constrain the evolution and origin of the Azores Plateau. We expect that the petrological and geochemical data and age determinations from lavas from the stratigraphic profiles confirm our observations that samples from the East Azores

Fracture Zone represent normal oceanic crust, likely between 10 Ma and 46 Ma, that have not been influenced by a postulated Azores plume head whereas those lavas observed and sampled at Princesa Alice Bank cover the transition from the sheeted dike complex of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge crust into aphanitic lava flows that could potentially have alkaline compositions due to formation in the intraplate area. We expect that the geochemical composition of the lower lavas indicates the highest degrees of partial melting of the Azores Plateau lavas. In addition, their ages will provide information when the first alkali, intraplate-related eruptions occurred. Comparing these to the samples from the profiles along the Terceira Rift, i.e. the Hirondele Basin stratigraphic profiles will, for the first time allow to develop a consistent model of the formation of the Azores Plateau. Comparing these to lavas from the youngest eruptions at Serreta, Sete Cidades, João de Castro and Capelinhos will in addition allow to better constrain the long-term changes in composition and geodynamic evolution of the Azores. We expect the petrological and volcanological data, along with the shipboard information (e.g., bathymetric data) to provide enough material for the publication of 5-6 manuscripts in international peer-reviewed journals.

For the volcanological observations we plan to compare the variably vesicular and shaped clasts from the 1998-2001 Serreta eruptions with the floating lava balloons sampled in January 1999 from the sea surface and described by Kueppers et al. (2012) to determine the cooling rates and geochemical changes of this eruption. The textural comparison of submarine and subaerial deposits of fall and pyroclastic density current deposits will provide evidence for the transport and emplacement processes as a function of the viscosity of the ambient medium (air vs. water). Subaerially emplaced counterparts will be the 1958/59 Capelinhos deposits (Klapper et al., 2010) and the 2006 Tungurahua (Ecuador) deposits (Douillet et al., 2013; Douillet et al., 2014). The morphologic and textural study of glassy fragments in the unconsolidated ash deposits will provide additional information on the bubble wall thickness and the formation of secondary bubbles. The question addressed with the samples obtained during M128 will also allow constraining whether the water depth affected the cooling rate of submarine quenched glass, which will be measured by differential scanning calorimetry. Finally, an experimental study on the reproducibility of bubble features will reveal whether the dm- to m-sized clasts taken at João do Castro and Serreta originate from magmatic gasses or sediments.

The stratigraphic profile sampled within Princesa Alice Bank represents a >1 km section through pervasively altered upper crust, ranging from quartz-epidote veined greenschist-facies rocks to completely clay-altered basalts. Petrological studies of these rocks will allow us to assess the conditions, directions, and magnitudes of geochemical exchange between seawater and the upper crust of the Azores Plateau.

6 Ship's Meteorological Station

(H. Rentsch, A. Raeke)

During the departure from Ponta Delgada on 2nd of July 2016 - the beginning of cruise M128 - and until next day, the high of the Azores and a strong inversion of temperature characterised the

weather. There was a strong free inversion of temperature with nearly overcast conditions below the top of inversion. At this time often drizzle was observed by the meteorological instruments of RV METEOR. There were mainly northerly winds of 4 to 5 Beaufort (Bft), waves did not exceed 1.5 m, and additionally a northerly swell below 1 m was observed.

Week of 04.07.2016 – 10.07.2016

Situated nearly in the centre of the Azores high the week started with many clouds below a strong temperature inversion. Occasionally, some showers of rain were observed in the vicinity of the ship. A northerly sea and swell of 0.5 to 1 m caused an almost calm sea. A northerly wind, and later an easterly wind of 4 to 5 Bft were registered. On 5th of July clouds of a warm front from a weak frontal system were approaching and passed the whole Azores islands and the ship slowly. Together with some drizzle we measured southerly winds of 5 Bft and gusts up to 6 Bft (22 knots), the sea rose up to 2 m, and the swell remained below 1.5 m coming from southerly, sometimes westerly directions. The visibility was bad and some fog and fog patches were temporarily seen until next day in the morning.

On the rear side of weakening fronts a mixture of sun and clouds, south-westerly winds of 3 to 4 Bft, and waves up to 2.5 m dominated the sea weather conditions between Tuesday, 5th and Friday 7th of July. During the afternoon hours in the shadow of the island of Pico the cold front of a new low pressure system passed us without showers. Due to wind from the mountains the south-westerly winds rose up to 7 Bft, gusts were seen up to 8 Bft during crossing of the cold front on 8th of July around 13:00 UTC (forecast of model EZMW: 5-6 Bft). We observed total waves up to 3.5 m (model of IPMA: 2.5 m). These conditions stopped the diving of ROV QUEST for that day. One hour after the passage of the front we measured decreasing winds of 5-6 Bft and a swell only up to 2.5 m. During the 09th and 10th of July a weakening and undulating cold front caused rain and drizzle in our working areas. We measured winds from 3 to 4 Bft from westerly and subsequently southerly directions; slowly decreasing significant waves did not exceed 2 m.

Week of 11.07.2016 – 17.07.2016

At the beginning of the new week a weak front was active, mostly broken clouds and only seldom light drizzle were registered, especially together with foggy conditions. The wind was variable between easterly 4 Bft and 2 Bft from south-westerly directions (land-sea wind effects), all depending of the time of the day and the ship's course in relation to the island Terceira. A general increase of pressure over the Azores caused a nearly calmed sea, waves of not more than 1.5 m from northerly directions were observed. During this period the ability to form mist and fog in the morning hours increased significantly. The following scenario continued until Friday, the 15th July: strong clouds of an inversion with mostly broken clouds, wind forces from 2 to 3 Bft at the beginning, later nearly 4 Bft, and mostly dry weather.

Between 16th and 17th July the influences of a low and the passage of a weak cold front changed the weather conditions significantly. Some precipitation, isolated showers and winds from W to

NW of 4-5 wind forces were measured, in connection with showers, we registered some gusts up to 6 Bft. Waves did not exceed 1.5 m until Sunday, 17th of July.

Week of 18.07.2016 – 24.07.2016

The Monday started friendly within a moist and maritime air mass, characterized by some cumulus clouds, which did not bring showers. We registered weak northerly winds and waves up to 1.5 m. From Monday to Tuesday another weak cold front caused some showers and wind forces of up to 5 Bft, during the day in connection with showers gusts from northerly directions and 6 Bft winds that were measured. On Tuesday during the evening the centre of the Azores high near 35°N 45°W strengthened and started to approach the ship's working area slowly arriving on Sunday. Together with mostly northerly-, later north-easterly winds around 3 Bft, seldom precipitation and wave heights below 1.5 m these were excellent working conditions for ROV and TV grab operations.

Week of 25.07.2016 – 27.07.2016

During the final three days aboard cloud coverage often changed quickly, but only some drizzle and isolated showers fell from stratocumulus clouds. The north-easterly trade winds were building up mainly on the south-easterly edge of the Azores high. At first, the trade wind came from north with 3 to 4 Bft later rising at times to wind force 5 Bft from northeast, additionally the swell reached nearly 1.5 m mostly from the northeast. On the day of arrival in Ponta Delgada (27.07.2016) the ship sailed under a cloudy sky, a south-easterly swell below 1 m was measured.

Station List M128

Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Start (Position)	Water depth [m]	Ende (UTC)	End Position	Water depth [m]	Water depth of sample [m]	Sample position	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples
Meteor														
Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)	Water depth [m]	Ende (UTC)	Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)	Water depth [m]	Water depth of sample [m]	Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples
M128_716_multibeam	02/07/2016	multibeam sonar	NW São Miguel	11:50	37°51.65' 25°57.04'	1309	13:47	37°56.67' 25°46.75'	822					
M128_717_TVG	02/07/2016	TV grab	NW ridge São Miguel	14:27	37°56.103' 25°51.380'	748	15:47	37°56.067' 25°51.372'	762	684	37°56.077' 25°51.375'	15:21		2 samples of basalt
M128_718_TVG	02/07/2016	TV grab	W/rift zone of São Miguel	16:22	37°53.402' 25°55.093'	361	18:50	37°53.523' 25°55.041'	302	302	37°53.523' 25°55.041'	18:27		1 sample of basalt
M128_719_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	NW of São Miguel	18:57	37°54.05' 25°55.91'	615	04:09	38°25.38' 26°51.09'	1277					
M128_720_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	E of João de Castro	05:20	38°12.53' 26°33.64'	418	08:00	38°11.62' 26°34.63'	779					
M128_721_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	E of João de Castro	06:18	38°12.73' 26°33.69'	483	06:41	38°12.73' 26°35.64'	216					
M128_722_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	E of João de Castro	07:05	38°12.711' 26°33.793'	421	08:45	38°12.618' 26°33.870'	350	343	38°12.619' 26°33.875'	08:30		3 total samples, glass, basaltic cок, fine material
M128_723_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	E of João de Castro	09:13	38°13.803' 26°34.309'	797	10:12	38°13.806' 26°34.310'	805					wrong depth information from bridge, actual water depth 41m; TVG crashed into ground; no serious damage, station cancelled
M128_724_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	N of João de Castro	10:49	38°12.72' 26°34.40'	211	12:20	38°12.72' 26°34.25'	253					2 basalt samples
M128_725_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	E flank of João de Castro	12:44	38°13.799' 26°34.393'	423	14:45	38°13.821' 26°34.392'	362	363	38°13.808' 26°34.393'	14:21		1 sample of ash luff
M128_726_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	N of João de Castro	15:05	38°13.83' 26°34.39'	208	15:52	38°15.78' 26°37.04'	208					
M128_727_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	rft NW of João de Castro	16:17	38°14.889' 26°38.104'	726	17:07	38°14.898' 26°38.106'	716	723	38°14.885' 26°38.105'	16:43		1 sample of ash luff
M128_728_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	small cone N of João de Castro	17:45	38°15.489' 26°38.314'	556	18:26	38°15.482' 26°38.317'	557	559	38°15.482' 26°38.317'	18:06		3 total samples, 2x glass flow, 1 ash luff
M128_729_TVG	03/07/2016	TV grab	NE flank of João de Castro	18:57	38°14.625' 26°34.633'	530	20:40	38°14.517' 26°34.622'	574	519	38°14.517' 26°34.622'	20:08		4 samples, 2x basalt, 1 carbonate, 1 ash luff
M128_730_multibeam	03/07/2016	multibeam sonar	NW to SW of João de Castro	22:28	38°15.03' 26°57.64'	1359	02:30	38°32.18' 26°38.807'	907					
M128_731_multibeam	04/07/2016	multibeam sonar	NW to SW of João de Castro	03:02	38°34.25' 26°36.45'	836	08:29	38°18.57' 26°57.607'	1112					
M128_733_ROV	04/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	NW top of João de Castro	09:35	38°12.555' 26°34.641'	292	18:05	38°12.719' 26°34.672'	177					12 total samples, lava fragments, lapilli luff, volcanoclastic breccia, coarse sand
M128_733_TVG	04/07/2016	TV grab	small cone S of João de Castro	19:21	38°10.625' 26°35.097'	832	21:41	38°10.895' 26°35.179'	678	684	38°10.735' 26°35.281'	21:18		1 deep sea coral: halysite
M128_734_TVG	04/07/2016	TV grab	cone S of João de Castro	22:12	38°10.104' 26°35.823'	1040	22:12	38°10.231' 26°35.838'	1097	1103	38°10.233' 26°35.831'	23:55		3 total samples, basalt, sand and ash
M128_735_TVG	05/07/2016	TV grab	ridge NW of João de Castro	01:42	38°16.761' 26°42.239'	1255	03:23	38°16.722' 26°42.392'	1230	1230	38°16.721' 26°42.392'	02:48		3 total samples, carbonate breccia, basalt and sand
M128_736_TVG	05/07/2016	TV grab	ridge NW of João de Castro	03:46	38°17.838' 26°42.381'	1366	05:59	38°17.741' 26°42.276'	1349	1353	38°17.753' 26°42.277'	05:22		1 sample, basaltic glass

Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Start (Position)	Water depth (m)	Ende (UTC)	End Position	Water depth (m)	Waterdepth of sample (m)	Sample position	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples
Meteor														
M128_737_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	cores NW of Lobo de Castro	06:24	38°18.867'	1343	07:56	38°18.663'	26°44.365'	1352	38°18.867'	07:20	sediments; malfunction of postiona	1 sample, volcanoclastica
M128_738_ROV	06/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	cliff N of Lobo de Castro	11:24	38°22.819'	2654	20:50	38°23.376'	26°32.696'	1937			biology in rocks; corals, sponges	13 total samples; basalt, 1 coral, 1 extra basalt sample (No. 14)
M128_739_multibeam	06/07/2016	multibeam sonar	N of Lobo de Castro	21:36	38°19.36'	2108	22:27	38°14.90'	26°35.86'	640				
M128_740_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	rfi NE of main rfi zone	23:03	38°16.221'	975	04:42 (06/07/16)	38°16.154'	26°36.849'	983	967	38°16.164'	fresh lava	1 sample of basalt
M128_741_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	N of Lobo de Castro	01:06	38°14.067'	293	02:05	38°14.029'	26°35.270'	283	264	38°14.036'	ash layers	1 sample of ash tuff
M128_742_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	W slope of Lobo de Castro	02:35	38°13.214'	467	05:35	38°11.837'	26°37.827'	522	523	38°13.202'	volcanic sand, glass, cpx, fishing line caught on TV grab and ship	2 total samples; fine volcanic sand into 3 bags; breccia/conglomerate
M128_743_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	ridge structure Lobo de Castro	06:14	38°12.707'	321	07:04	38°12.775'	26°34.046'	334	335	38°12.731'	In situ pillow segment	2 total samples; lava fragments
M128_744_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	core SE of Lobo de Castro	07:19	38°12.240'	430	08:02	38°12.246'	26°33.424'	425	429	38°12.262'	lava pieces; biology (corals, sponges); fresh rocks	3 total samples; lava fragments
M128_745_ROV	06/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	N flank of Lobo de Castro	10:29	38°15.368'	892	18:46	38°14.742'	26°36.356'	564			basaltic rocks; lot of biology on samples;	13 total samples; basaltic rocks; pillow, ashes; 3 biology samples
M128_746_TVG	06/07/2016	TV grab	core W of E rfi zone NW of Lobo de Castro	20:38	38°17.476'	1356	22:39	38°17.367'	26°37.888'	1416	1355	38°17.429'	dark ash	1 samples volcanic ash
M128_747_multibeam	06/07/2016	multibeam sonar	W of Lobo de Castro, southeastern flanks of Graciosa	22:56	38°19.06'	1961	05:26 (07/07/16)	38°48.77'	27°35.67'	1789				
M128_748_multibeam	07/07/2016	multibeam sonar	southeastern flanks of Graciosa	05:52	38°48.53'	780	07:24	38°48.45'	27°25.21'	356				
M128_749_TVG	07/07/2016	TV grab	Serrata rfi	08:19	38°50.601'	1146	10:02	38°50.715'	27°30.418'	1224	1185	38°50.631'	pillow pieces to 50cm, older but not altered	3 total samples; pillow/basalt
M128_750_multibeam	07/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Serrata rfi	11:12	38°49.42'	700	11:43	38°50.79'	27°31.27'	1572				
M128_751_ROV	07/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	N of Serrata rfi	14:08	38°48.125'	612	20:14	38°48.827'	27°28.276'	484			biology on samples (corals, sponges, bryozoa, molluscs)	12 total samples; basalt and fine material
M128_752_TVG	07/07/2016	TV grab	NW Serrata rfi	21:55	38°52.357'	1720	23:53	38°52.338'	27°32.509'	1724	1756	38°52.356'	lots of sediment; smaller dark blocks; TVG empty	no sample
M128_753_TVG	07/07/2016	TV grab	Ridge NW of 751_ROV	00:29	38°48.846'	746	01:22	38°49.836'	27°29.272'	765	765	38°49.847'	rough surface; thin sediment layer; may be pillows	2 total samples; basalt/pillow
M128_754_multibeam	08/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Pico Ridge	05:57	38°18.90'	397	07:56	38°24.47'	27°58.64'	204				
M128_755_ROV	08/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	Pico Ridge	09:26	38°23.317'	555	13:33	38°23.253'	27°56.615'	452			coral debris; basaltic lava fragments; carbonate	8 total samples; lava fragments; carbonate; volcanoclastic rock; 2 biology samples
M128_756_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	Pico Ridge	14:40	38°24.051'	436	15:28	38°24.051'	27°57.532'	215	216	38°24.051'	biogenic sediment with volcanic rock fragment	1 sample carbonate granitstone
M128_757_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	Pico Ridge	16:08	38°21.886'	308	16:54	38°21.882'	27°53.142'	310	309	38°21.889'	unconsolidated coral; no sample	no rock sample; 1 sample of coral debris

Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Latitude (°N) [Longitude (°W)]	Water depth (m)	Ende (UTC)	End Position	Water depth (m)	Waterdepth of sample (m)	Latitude (°N) [Longitude (°W)]	Sample position	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples
M128_790_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	mount on Pico Ridge	17:14	38°20.902' 27°52.734'	292.5	18:30	38°20.865' 27°52.695'	304	302	38°20.851' 27°52.732'	18:20	one piece of lava, altered with biology	1 sample volcanic breccia	
M128_799_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	volcanic mounds on Pico Ridge	19:01	38°19.916' 27°51.638'	370	21:01	38°19.774' 027°51.511'	450				too hard surface, empty TV-Grab	no sample	
M128_790_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	Pico Ridge	21:25	38°18.813' 27°50.603'	397	22:42	38°18.818' 27°50.495'	460	402	38°18.818' 27°50.507'	22:24	hard surface, carbonate crust	2 total samples, basaltic rock and volcanoclastic breccia	
M128_791_TVG	08/07/2016	TV grab	Pico Ridge	23:00	38°18.133' 27°49.460'	665	00:27 (09/07/16)	38°18.121' 27°49.458'	688	667	38°18.123' 27°49.458'	23:53	too hard surface, empty TV-Grab	no sample	
M128_792_multibeam	09/07/2016	multibeam sonar	SW of Graciosa / Northeast of Faial	00:40	38°19.27' 27°52.12'	713	01:37	38°22.55' 27°56.78'	555						
M128_793_multibeam	09/07/2016	multibeam sonar		01:46	38°21.76' 27°56.45'	765	02:39	38°18.46' 27°53.05'	922						
M128_794_ROV	09/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	N flank Terceira basin	09:48	39°01.476' 27°30.675'	1733	19:22	39°02.090' 27°30.172'	1028					lava flows, lava tubes, biology on some rocks	12 total samples, lava fragments, pillows, 2 biology samples
M128_795_multibeam	09/07/2016	multibeam sonar		20:42	39°02.64' 27°29.59'	797	04:00	39°02.84' 27°29.31'	848						
M128_796_multibeam	09/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Serreta	04:15	39°01.37' 27°27.19'	1485	06:09	38°52.81' 27°22.72'	633						
M128_797_ROV	10/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	central Serreta volcanic ridge	08:30	38°47.457' 27°27.988'	377	19:14	38°47.748' 27°27.623'	242					loose deposits of lapilli, basalt outcrops, lots of biology	15 total samples, fresh lava, basalt, 2 biology samples
M128_798_multibeam	10/07/2016	multibeam sonar	NW of Graciosa	20:33	38°48.51' 27°29.26'	489	22:07	38°48.15' 27°29.87'	396						
M128_798_TVG	10/07/2016	TV grab	Serreta	22:37	38°47.795' 27°28.898'	195	00:11 (11/07/16)	38°47.199' 27°28.714'	200	204	38°47.192' 27°28.725'	23:54	very hard surface, steep slopes	4 total samples, 2x pillow, 2x volcanic breccia	
M128_774_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	Serreta	00:42	38°48.335' 27°30.854'	551	01:43	38°48.320' 27°30.845'	551	552	38°48.324' 27°30.844'	01:08	problems with TV grab's battery,	no sample	
M128_771_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	Serreta	02:05	38°48.324' 27°30.847'	552	03:11	38°48.319' 27°30.798'	356	567	38°48.314' 27°30.810'	02:50	pieces of lava	2 total samples, lava balloons	
M128_772_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	Serreta NW crater	03:43	38°48.127' 27°29.107'	360	04:47	38°48.144' 27°29.150'	356	344	38°48.144' 27°29.150'	04:22	several pieces of lava	4 total samples, basalt	
M128_773_multibeam	11/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Serreta to W of Graciosa	05:37	38°51.54' 27°25.94'	943	07:30	38°45.00' 27°30.40'	1603						
M128_774_ROV	11/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	central Serreta volcanic ridge	11:40	38°47.466' 27°28.148'	329	18:59	38°47.667' 27°28.832'	313					biology, bacterial mats (former hydrothermal activity?)	6 total samples, lava, lava bombs, lapilli, fine material
M128_775_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	Serreta ridge (SW part)	20:46	38°47.708' 27°29.127'	347	21:39	38°47.708' 27°29.124'	356	305	38°47.719' 27°29.125'	21:05	fresh lava balloons	2 total samples, lava balloons	
M128_776_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	E part of central Serreta volcanic ridge	22:05	38°47.854' 27°28.707'	372	23:15	38°47.873' 27°28.732'	400	353	38°47.870' 27°28.719'	22:54	vesicular lava fragments	2 total samples, basaltic lava fragments	
M128_777_TVG	11/07/2016	TV grab	W edge of central Serreta volcanic ridge	23:32	38°47.936' 27°29.197'	284	00:21 (12/07/16)	38°47.929' 27°29.242'	303	286	38°47.941' 27°29.199'	23:50	Position of ship's position been taken for sample locally	2 total samples, basaltic lava fragments	
M128_778_TVG	12/07/2016	TV grab	WSW Serreta Ridge	00:38	38°48.059' 27°29.505'	321	01:04	38°48.050' 27°29.509'	326	324	38°48.059' 27°29.507'	00:50	several pieces of lava balloons and fine material	3 total samples, lava fragments/lava balloons	

Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Start (Position)	Water depth (m)	Ende (UTC)	End Position	Water depth (m)	Waterdepth of sample (m)	Sample position	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples
Meteor					Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)			Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)		Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)				
M128_775_TVG	12/07/2016	TV grab	W end Serratia Ridge	01:37	38°48.176' 27°30.078'	313	02:29	38°48.167' 27°30.037'	317	315	38°48.169' 27°30.041'	02:11	lot of biology, ropes, no positional, small pieces of lava with corals	1 sample, basaltic lava
M128_780_TVG	12/07/2016	TV grab	S Serratia Ridge	03:36	38°47.024' 27°27.249'	356	04:22	38°47.046' 27°27.258'	356	352	38°47.046' 27°27.258'	04:01	lots of corals, no positional pieces of lava ballions	2 ball samples, basaltic lava fragments
M128_781_ROV	12/07/2016	ROV/Quest 4000	End of Serratia volcanic ridge	12:01	38°46.981' 27°27.519'	455	20:19	38°47.740' 27°28.102'	334				biology on rocks, some rocks covered with hydrothermal sediment	11 total samples, pillow, lapilli, lava fragments
M128_782_TVG	12/07/2016	TV grab	NW of Terceira	21:46	38°52.662' 27°25.450'	975	23:32	38°52.676' 27°25.488'	1007	975	38°52.674' 27°25.474'	23:04	3 lated grabs. Sediment hard stuff at some places, not much topography	1 sample, tiny piece of lava fragment
M128_783_TVG	12/07/2016	TV grab	NW of Terceira	23:58	38°53.216' 27°25.068'	985	01:28	38°53.246' 27°25.070'	977				empty grab, station cancelled	no sample
M128_784_multibeam	12/07/2016	multibeam sonar	N of Faialhead to MAR	01:47	38°55.77' 27°24.08'	1013	04:01 (13:07:16)	39°06.13' 28°30.11'	2440					
M128_785_TVG	13/07/2016	TV grab	Segment near MAR, flank of seamount	13:24	39°13.786' 29°22.050'	1172	15:13	39°13.760' 29°22.001'	1178	1151	39°13.759' 29°22.004'	14:34	one tiny piece of black fine grained lava hosted in sand	1 sample of fine biogenic sand and fragments of lava
M128_786_multibeam	13/07/2016	multibeam sonar	track to MAR	05:27	39°07.73' 28°12.52'	803	07:42	39°08.95' 28°13.17'	987					
M128_787_ROV	14/07/2016	ROV/Quest 4000	Graciosa Ridge	09:18	39°07.029' 28°11.518'	670	19:23	39°07.818' 28°11.319'	503				lot of biology on rocks, carbonate debris.	14 total samples, volcanoclastic breccia, carbonates, 1 biology sample
M128_788_multibeam	14/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Graciosa Ridge	20:35	39°06.20' 28°13.46'	1309	07:00	38°59.19' 28°13.439'	813					
M128_789_ROV	15/07/2016	ROV/Quest 4000	N wall of Hierodolite Basin	09:54	38°23.336' 28°32.685'	1985	18:29	38°23.736' 26°52.444'	1270				biology on rocks (corals, sponges, dams)	22 total samples, pillow lavas, vesicular lava fragments, fine layered sediment, carbonate, 2 biology samples
M128_790_multibeam	16/07/2016	multibeam sonar	W of São Miguel	20:18	38°27.05' 28°27.88'	1552	12:50	37°53.02' 25°55.911'	615				lot of biology on rocks	8 total samples, lava fragments, volcanoclastic breccia, 1 biology sample
M128_791_ROV	17/07/2016	ROV/Quest 4000	ridge W of Sabrina	10:48	37°53.377' 25°55.040'	400	15:07	37°53.567' 25°54.887'	278				lot of biology on rocks	
M128_792_TVG	17/07/2016	TV grab	cone SW of São Cidadas	22:47	37°50.667' 25°55.889'	750	00:59 (18:07:16)	37°50.871' 25°55.866'	751	733	37°50.666' 25°55.882'	00:27	sediment (mud), partly biology on seafloor	2 cups fine material
M128_793_TVG	18/07/2016	TV grab	cone WNW of São Cidadas	01:42	37°55.289' 25°52.274'	749	02:55	37°55.317' 25°52.228'	750	723	37°55.330' 25°52.215'	02:32	smooth seafloor covered with fine sediment, but difficult to grab, probably ash layers, piece of consolidated ash	1 sample, consolidated ash layers
M128_794_TVG	18/07/2016	TV grab	crater structure NW of São Cidadas	03:20	37°56.360' 25°50.123'	368	04:48	37°56.307' 25°50.117'	360	365	37°56.337' 25°50.046'	04:30	biology on rocks, cliffs	1 sample, lava fragment
M128_795_TVG	18/07/2016	TV grab	Ridge NW of São Miguel	05:07	37°57.263' 25°50.779'	642	06:31	37°57.199' 25°50.944'	621	639	37°57.213' 25°50.748'	06:02	Sediment cover, corals, quite flat	1 sample, different carbonates
M128_796_ROV	18/07/2016	ROV/Quest 4000	W flank São Miguel off Mosteiros	09:00	37°55.826' 25°51.482'	753	17:54	37°56.101' 28°51.024'	547				biology on rocks, some ash	14 total samples, lava and pillow samples, mostly abyssic and vesicular, 1 carbonate-ash mix, 2 biology samples
M128_797_TVG	18/07/2016	TV grab	Ridge on N flank Hierodolite Basin	21:34	38°14.933' 26°14.041'	686	22:37	38°14.929' 26°14.956'	677	655	38°14.918' 26°14.049'	22:14	very hard, no biology	1 sample, possibly gneiss, diopside?
M128_798_TVG	18/07/2016	TV grab	Ridge on N flank Hierodolite Basin	23:05	38°13.827' 26°13.282'	441	00:42 (19:07:16)	38°13.223' 26°13.217'	428	414	38°13.736' 26°13.212'	00:28	hard surface, no morphology, lot of rads	1 sample, carbonate
M128_799_TVG	19/07/2016	TV grab	Ridge on N flank Hierodolite Basin	01:19	38°11.808' 26°12.580'	770	02:38	38°11.818' 26°12.827'	762	731	38°11.823' 26°12.616'	02:13	steep topography, problems to grab, lot of coral debris	1 sample, carbonate mudstone

Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Water depth (m)	Ende (UTC)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Water depth (m)	Water depth of sample (m)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Size/number of samples	
M128_800_TVG	19/07/2016	TV grab	Rift structure of documented 18th century eruption	03:36	38°10.539'	26°03.048'	883	04:34	38°10.538'	26°03.052'	883	874	38°10.531'	26°03.041'	04:04	fresh rocks, maybe pillow, biology on rocks	1 sample, pillow fragment	
M128_801_TVG	19/07/2016	TV grab	ESE of 800_TVG	04:52	38°10.169'	26°01.728'	890	05:58	38°10.166'	26°01.725'	887	870	38°10.166'	26°01.716'	05:29	carbonate	1 sample, corals	
M128_802_ROV	19/07/2106	ROV Quest 4000	S rift wall Hondele Basin	10:20	37°49.604'	26°04.334'	2255	17:03	37°49.445'	26°04.620'	1444					some coral debris, sediment, flow and dike structure	10 total samples, lava and pillow fragments	
M128_803_multibeam	19/07/2016		transit S wall of Hondele Basin to S border of Azores Plateau	19:07	37°50.96'	26°07.37'	1739	07:45 (0007/16)	36°50.58'	27°26.48'	3966							
M128_804_ROV	20/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	East Azores Fracture Zone	12:34	36°51.532'	27°25.796'	2786	18:36	36°52.313'	27°25.620'	2345						8 total samples, peridotite, carbonate, sediment	
M128_805_multibeam	20/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Azores Fracture Zone	21:44	36°38.98'	27°28.41'	3040	07:55	36°52.38'	27°25.79'	2316							
M128_806_TVG	21/07/2016	TV grab	Azores Fracture Zone	12:10	36°52.243'	27°25.709'	2382	14:35	36°52.253'	27°25.670'	2460	2464m		36°52.232'	27°25.702'	13:50	rocks covered with fine sediment, different to assess morphology, a few fragments of altered peridotite recovered, sediment	4 total samples, peridotite
M128_807_TVG	21/07/2016	TV grab	East Azores Fracture Zone, steep cliff section N-S	14:55	36°52.257'	27°25.664'	2312	16:55	36°52.256'	27°25.677'	2352	2395		36°52.266'	27°25.657'	15:44	rough morphology of outcrop, thin sediment cover/pillows, large pieces of (altered) peridotite - in situ	5 total samples, peridotite
M128_808_TVG	21/07/2016	TV grab	East Azores Fracture Zone, steep cliff section N-S	17:10	36°52.55'	27°25.56'	2119	19:49	36°52.56'	27°25.55'	2101						empty grab	no sample
M128_809_multibeam	21/07/2016	multibeam sonar	East Azores Fracture Zone to Princess Alice Bank	20:00	36°52.59'	27°26.02'	2233	07:37	38°11.58'	29°33.28'	2400						less biology on rocks, sediment covered outcrops	13 total samples, altered basalt, 2 biology samples
M128_810_ROV	22/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	Rift of Princess Alice Bank	10:28	38°11.779'	29°33.673'	2536	18:36	38°12.211'	39°33.550'	1723							
M128_811_TVG	22/07/2016	TV grab	cone SW Capelinhos	23:57	38°36.878'	28°54.912'	748	00:47 (2307/16)	38°36.877'	28°54.906'	743	720		38°36.888'	28°54.902'	00:25	less topography, shallow, ash and volcanic fragments	2 total samples, lava fragments
M128_812_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	ridge NW of Capelinhos	01:14	38°37.277'	28°53.978'	527	02:06	38°37.278'	28°53.978'	524	527		38°37.288'	28°53.982'	01:46	maybe large pillows, ash	1 sample of consolidated ash
M128_813_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	NW of Capelinhos	02:23	38°37.277'	28°53.975'	524	03:25	38°37.270'	28°53.952'	523	519		38°37.280'	28°53.953'	03:03	steep slope, old reef border? lava fragments	1 fresh lava sample
M128_814_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	W end of Capelinhos	03:45	38°37.401'	28°54.537'	665	04:25	38°37.288'	28°54.537'	680	683		38°37.402'	28°54.538'	04:05	no position, steep topography, pillow-like structures, fresh lava flows	2 total samples, lava fragments
M128_815_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	cone eastern Capelinhos	04:52	38°36.344'	28°51.689'	144	05:31	38°36.386'	28°51.689'	186	146		38°36.340'	28°51.671'	05:19	no position, fresh lava flows	1 large piece of lava with hole of biology
M128_816_multibeam	23/07/2016	multibeam sonar	Capelinhos	06:00	38°37.95'	28°55.29'	1333	07:42	38°37.37'	28°55.58'	1406							
M128_817_ROV	23/07/2016	ROV Quest 4000	Cador de Terra	08:54	38°34.43'	29°06.80'	939	19:00	38°33.95'	29°06.55'	975						13 total samples	
M128_818_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	sampling Capelinhos	20:48	38°36.139'	28°51.815'	341	21:24	38°36.139'	28°51.815'	339	333		38°36.149'	28°51.818'	21:08	flat surface, black lapilli & ash	2 total sample, glass, lava fragment
M128_819_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	sampling Capelinhos	21:57	38°36.625'	28°51.546'	152	22:25	38°36.625'	28°51.547'	152	142		38°36.618'	28°51.566'	22:08	flat surface, ripples, consolidated ash, fishing net caught in TV grab	2 total sample, ash
M128_820_TVG	23/07/2016	TV grab	cone W of Capelinhos	22:49	38°37.107'	28°53.501'	419	23:29	38°37.103'	28°53.503'	402	427		38°37.102'	28°53.505'	23:08	pillow-like structures, lot of biology	1 total sample, pillow

Meteor	Station	Date (UTC)	Gear	Location	Start (UTC)	Start Position	Water depth [m]	Ende (UTC)	End Position	Water depth [m]	Water depth of sample [m]	Sample position	Sample time (UTC)	comments	Stasiun number of samples
						Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)			Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)			Latitude (°N) Longitude (°W)			
	M128_821_TVG	25072016	TV grab	cone western part of Capelinhos	23:48	38°37.473' 28°53.609'	442	00:29 (24:07:16)	38°37.470' 28°53.611'	446	445	38°37.470' 28°53.610'	00:13 (24:07)	no position, ash layers, partly glassy	1 fine Material, 4 total sample
	M128_822_TVG	24072016	TV grab	northern part of Capelinhos	01:17	38°38.029' 28°52.279'	617	02:08	38°38.020' 28°52.279'	610	609	38°38.023' 28°52.279'	01:47	no Position, layered ash, lava fragment	3 total samples, layered ash, lava fragment
	M128_823_multibeam	24072016	multibeam sonar	southeast of falal, Condor de Terra	03:07	38°31.04' 28°58.11'	282	07:12	38°10.63' 29°28.95'	1650					
	M128_824_ROV	24072016	ROV Quest 4000	Rift of Princess Alice Bank	10:03	38°12.060' 29°33.540'	1980	18:33	38°12.500' 29°33.560'	1379				continuation of 810-ROV	13 total samples, 12 geological one biological
	M128_825_multibeam	24072016	multibeam sonar	Princess Alice bank to N of Capelinhos	19:56	38° 14.02' 29°33.74'	1216	00:50 (25:07:16)	38°39.65' 29°07.01'	1935					
	M128_826_TVG	25072016	TV grab	rft NW of Capelinhos	01:00	38°39.467' 28°52.360'	746	02:43	38°39.434' 28°52.362'	728	708	38°38.428' 28°52.372'	02:20	flat hard surface	1 cup of sediment
	M128_827_TVG	25072016	TV grab	rft zone N of Capelinhos	03:16	38°40.766' 28°47.506'	659	04:11	38°40.699' 28°47.500'	660	647	38°40.692' 28°47.509'	03:49	no morphology, red, hard surface	2 cups fine material,
	M128_828_multibeam	25072016	multibeam sonar	Rift of São Jorge	05:47	38°47.97' 28°29.10'	1084	07:47	38°47.48' 28°31.10'	1097					
	M128_829_ROV	25072016	ROV Quest 4000	W Rift of São Jorge	09:31	38°46.440' 28°27.710'	963	18:25	38°47.640' 28°27.580'	472				mostly sediments, some pillow-lava outcrops	6 samples
	M128_830_TVG	25072016	TV grab	Rift Zone W of São Jorge	19:38	38°47.769' 28°27.161'	688	20:27	38°47.772' 28°27.163'	690	683	38°47.764' 28°27.177'	19:57	some topography, platy surface, problems to grab	just biology samples (corals)
	M128_831_TVG	25072016	TV grab	Rift Zone W of São Jorge	20:48	38°47.143' 28°27.729'	476	21:59	38°47.241' 28°27.299'	558	545	38°47.238' 28°27.753'	21:38	very steep, carbonate crust	1 total sample carbonate
	M128_832_TVG	25072016	TV grab	Rift Zone W of São Jorge	22:20	38°47.024' 28°28.628'	332	23:06	38°46.975' 28°28.615'	335	342	38°46.968' 28°28.625'	22:50	best topography, carbonate crust, biology	just biology samples (corals)
	M128_833_TVG	25072016	TV grab	Eastern Rift Zone W of São Jorge	23:30	38°46.288' 28°24.965'	261	00:17 (28:07:16)	38°46.255' 28°25.055'	273	266	38°46.247' 28°25.061'		best topography, carbonate crust, biology	3 total samples, volcanoclastic breccia with lava fragments and carbonate
	M128_834_TVG	28072016	TV grab	Eastern Rift Zone W of São Jorge	00:34	38°47.109' 28°42.254'	270	01:27	38°47.070' 28°42.260'	276	267	38°47.064' 28°42.272'	01:12	best topography, carbonate crust, biology	2 total samples, volcanic rock
	M128_835_multibeam	28072016	multibeam sonar	São Jorge, Fall southern rift shoulder of Terceira rift	02:13	38°49.13' 28°41.09'	1108	27:07 (2016 03:52)	37°44.630' 26°15.061'	935				final station	

8 Data and Sample Storage and Availability

All hydroacoustic data collected from Hamburg University are currently being processed. Data are stored in facilities of the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum. Metadata of the onboard DSHIP-System will be uploaded to a World Data Center (e.g. PANGAEA) which provides a long-term archive and access to the data (contact: christoph.beier@fau.de). Multi-beam field data are stored at the bathymetric data centre of the Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrografie, however, these data are protected until the end of 2019. The petrological samples are available at the GeoZentrum Nordbayern, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, the biological sample material will be available at the Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre, University of the Azores DOP/UAç and the Department of Oceanography and Fisheries of the University of the Azores. The petrological and geochemical data will be published in peer-reviewed journals and will be available in international databases such as GEOROC and PetDB.

Type	Database	Available	Free Access	Contact
		Date	Date	E-Mail
raw data, multibeam data, DSHP	PANGAEA, BFSH	March 2017	September 2019	christoph.beier@fau.de
Petrological samples	GZN, Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	June 2016	September 2019	christoph.beier@fau.de
Biological samples	MARE & DOP/UAç	June 2016	September 2019	irisfs@gmail.com cerqueira.mt@gmail.com fempera@hotmail.com

9 Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the help of the Foreign Office in Berlin, the German Embassy in Lisbon and the Leitstelle Deutsche Forschungsschiffe in Hamburg in achieving the research permission. The cruise was financed by the German Research Foundation (DFG). We thank captain Jan Schubert and his crew for their help in carrying out a successful cruise and for the pleasant and professional atmosphere on RV METEOR. We acknowledge the help and support of the captain and crew of M128 also during the ROV and TV grab operations. We also greatly acknowledge their support and help during the “30-yrs RV METEOR” guest cruise.

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